

TransformAr

Accelerating and upscaling transformational adaptation in
Europe: demonstration of water-related innovation
packages

Results on the public acceptance and preferences Deliverable 6.1

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon H2020 innovation action programme under grant agreement 101036683.

Deliverable Number and Name	D6.1 - Results on the public acceptance and preferences
Work Package	WP6– Acceptance, building and exploitation of innovation packages
Dissemination Level	PU
Author(s)	Andrea Bigano, Anna Alberini, Adan Martinez Cruz
Primary Contact and Email	Andrea Bigano, andrea.bigano@cmcc.it
Date Due	M16
Date Submitted	31 May 2023; revised version 30 May 2024, final version 1 September 2024
File Name	TransformAr-WP6-D6.1- Results on the public acceptance and preferences – v2 – 28-08-2024
Status	V2
Reviewed by (if applicable)	Laura Enthoven (UA)
Suggested citation	Bigano, A., Alberini, A. and Martinez Cruz, A. (2022) Results on the public acceptance and preferences. TransformAr Deliverable 6.1, H2020 grant no. 101036683

© TransformAr Consortium, 2021

This deliverable contains original unpublished work except when indicated otherwise. Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation, or both. Reproduction is authorised if the source is acknowledged.

This document has been prepared in the framework of the European project TransformAr. This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 innovation action programme under grant agreement no. 101036683.

The sole responsibility for the content of this publication lies with the authors. It does not necessarily represent the opinion of the European Union. Neither the EASME nor the European Commission are responsible for any use that may be made of the information contained therein.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

LIST OF ACRONYMS.....	4
ACKNOWLEDGMENTS.....	4
EXECUTIVE SUMMARY.....	5
1.0 INTRODUCTION.....	7
2.0 LITERATURE REVIEW.....	8
3.0 METHODOLOGICAL APPROACH	11
3.1 Theoretical approach for Discrete Choice Experiments.....	12
3.2 The questionnaire design	12
3.3.1 Scoping Stage.....	13
3.3.2 Early development stage	14
3.3.3 Improving the questionnaire building on one-on one tests.	14
3.3.4 The final questionnaire	16
3.3 The experimental design.....	20
3.4 The econometric model	25
4.0 DATA	27
4.1 The dataset.....	27
5.0 RESULTS	34
5.1 Split samples and the relevance of scope	34
5.2 Pooled Sample Regressions	34
5.3 Country-specific Regressions	39
5.4 . Program Effectiveness: Constrained Regressions.....	39
6.0 CONCLUSIONS	42
REFERENCES	45
ANNEX 1: THE QUESTIONNAIRE.....	49
ANNEX 2: DETAILS ON ONE-ON-ONE TESTS	76

LIST OF ACRONYMS

Acronym	Explanation
WTP	Willingness to Pay
DCE	Discrete Choice Experiment
CAWI	Computer Assisted Web Interviewing
GHG	Green-House Gasses
CO2	Carbon dioxide
OECD-ISCED	Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development - International Standard Classification of Education
PPP	Purchasing Power Parity
cdf	cumulative distribution function
C.I.	Confidence Interval

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

Notwithstanding the long time it required for completion, this research has been very instructive and interesting. We would like to thank our project partners, for their precious feedback and support: the University of Antwerp (we are particularly grateful to Amalie Bjørnåvold for her unvaluable help with the development of the questionnaire, the Norwegian translation, and the revision of the first draft of this deliverable, to Laura Enthoven for her very accurate revision of the updated second draft, and to Jan Cools for his comments and guidance as WP6 leader); the University of Vigo (Andrea Ogando Vidal, Lucía Fraga Lago and colleagues), for their feedback on an early version of the questionnaire; all demo partners, whose feedback helped adding concreteness to our depiction of adaptation actions; and all partners taking part to the workshop on discrete choice experiments held at the consortium General Assembly in Guadeloupe. We are also very grateful to all test participants: the interaction with lay people during the one-on-one tests has been quite illuminating, as all participants provided us their sincere and well-thought feedback, which in more than one occasion included valuable intuitions that forced us to reconsider and revisit our questions. Many thanks also to all our colleagues in the CMCC-TransformAr team for the interesting conversations, in particular to Antonio Trabucco e Andrea Rivoecchi for their help with GIS-based computation of our distance-from-the-coast variable. Finally, we are very grateful to the Dynata team for their highly professional technical assistance during the design and deployment of the survey.

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

One of the TransformAr project's objectives is to understand the degree of acceptance of adaptation solutions by the public. This is the main focus of Work Package 6, and task T.6.1 on the 'Econometric analysis of acceptance and preferences of adaptive solutions' contributes to it by eliciting the public's preferences for adaptation solutions and by estimating the willingness-to-pay (WTP) for adaptation measures and packages across Europe. To derive such estimates, we performed a Discrete Choice Experiment (DCE) on a sample of over 9000 households in six European countries. This deliverable describes the methods and the results of this empirical study.

Surveys designed to elicit people's preferences and attitudes are widely used in empirical environmental economics studies, as environmental goods typically do not have a market, and hence assigning them a meaningful economic value cannot rely directly on market prices. Discrete choice experiments are a widely used method in the environmental economics literature on non-market goods evaluation. In empirical studies assessing the public perception of climate change policies, the application of DCE methods to adaptation policies and measures is scarcer compared to those related to mitigation. Most DCE studies on adaptation have a local focus and evaluate one or few specific adaptation measures to be deployed at a specific location, focusing, in most instances, on agricultural and coastal adaptation. To our knowledge, no studies are taking a broader stance and evaluating the WTP of the residents in one or more countries towards adaptation in general, or in the various sectors for which adaptation measures may be needed. Our study, which covers six European countries and six adaptation sectors, is a first attempt to arrive to such general WTP estimates.

Methods. We conducted a survey among 9072 (over 1500 per country) respondents in six European countries where TransformAr's demonstrators' adaptation solutions are implemented (namely, Greece, Spain, Italy, Finland, Norway and the United Kingdom). The survey was carried out by a survey company using Computer Assisted Web Interviewing (CAWI) procedures.

As noted above, Discrete Choice Experiments (DCEs) are our method of choice to assess the degree of acceptance of adaptation policy measures by Europeans. In a DCE setting, individual decisions about the object of the choice, be it a good, a service, or a policy action, are determined by its characteristics, or attributes. One of these attributes conveys the monetary cost for the respondent, for instance, in the form of taxes or higher prices of certain products. DCEs are based on data collected by asking survey respondents to indicate their preferences among several goods or policy options described by attributes. A status quo alternative is included to ensure that respondents are not forced to choose if they prefer not to. In our case, using a DCE allows us to gauge how much people are willing to pay for the implementation of an adaptation measure, or a combination of measures within a policy package.

Our questionnaire includes seven sections. After a few demographic questions needed to verify the sampling quotas, the focus progressively narrows from broad attitudes towards climate change to the more specific features of adaptation policies. The main section of the questionnaire is the discrete choice experiment, whereby we ask our respondents to choose between the status quo (in which no new tax is levied and no new adaptation policy is implemented) and a policy package described in terms the sectors covered (water

resources, surface water, sea level rise, agriculture, forests and fisheries) the kind of adaptation measure implemented, (infrastructure, nature-based or regulation), and the annual addition to income tax to be paid each year for the next ten years. Follow-up questions check whether respondents considered co-benefits of adaptation in their choice, and the attributes deemed most and least relevant for their choice. The choice experiment is repeated seven times with each respondent, varying the levels of the same or all attributes each time. The final section deals again with the socio-demographic features of the respondent's household. The questionnaire closes with a final question asking how likely the respondent thinks that the opinion expressed in the survey will be taken into account by policymakers.

Main Results. Our survey was carried out between October 23rd, 2023, and December 15th, 2023. We analysed our dataset using STATATM. Key parameters were significant and with the sign we expected. In particular, the coefficient on the cost of the policy program was negative and statistically significant. This allowed us to estimate overall WTP as well as sector-specific WTPs; however, estimating WTPs for different types of measures proved not feasible in most instances, as only the presence of infrastructure triggers a significant reaction.

Our most comprehensive WTP estimate, for policy packages covering all resources and sectors considered in the DCE, is quite high (EUR 1346 a year). In terms of sector-specific WTPs, we found a clear ranking of WTP across sectors: respondents care the most for adaptation for water supply, followed by surface waters, forests, agriculture, coastal areas, and fisheries. Restricting the sample to those who expect their answers to be taken into consideration by policymakers does not affect the ranking, but has a small, positive effect on WTPs. Results are also robust to excluding those respondents who voted in favour of the hypothetical program all seven times.

We found a very small (0.08) but significant Income elasticity of the WTP computed at the sample's average household. Having completed a university education results in a more sizeable effect on WTP, as university-educated respondents are willing to pay EUR 160 more for any adaptation program than persons with lower educational attainments.

The WTP for implementing adaptation policy packages varies noticeably depending on the targeted sectors and on the country in which policies are supposed to be implemented. Italy and the UK are the countries placing the highest value on protecting their coastlines, while the Italian respondents are the ones with the lowest degree of concern about agriculture. Adaptation policy targeting water supply, the most highly valued resource in all countries, reaches its top WTP in Spain.

Implications and recommendations. There are valuable takeaways for our project and for the EU adaptation policy in these results. From TransformAr's perspective, our WTP estimates provide the empirical basis for a comprehensive assessment of the acceptance of adaptation actions in Europe. We found a specification of our econometric estimations that can be used to perform a Benefit Transfer exercise to all other European countries to estimate the WTPs for adaptation across Europe. We report about this exercise in Deliverable D.6.2.

In terms of acceptance of adaptation policy actions, we can conclude that our demonstrators' adaptation solutions stand good chances to be warmly welcomed in the areas where they are being deployed, but those dealing with water resources are likely to meet the highest interest, and those dealing with fisheries are likely to trigger much less support within the public.

1.0 INTRODUCTION

TransformAr aims to demonstrate solutions and pathways that are highly relevant for climate and social resilience to achieve rapid and far-reaching transformational adaptation. This is done through a wide array of activities centred around the development, deployment, and testing of specific adaptation solutions in the EU. TransformAr's activities focus on providing the most complete knowledge base to stakeholders, policymakers and the public, to ensure that all the relevant information about opportunities, conditions and implications of adaptation options are available. Among others, Task T.6.1 of TransformAr aims to gauge public acceptance of climate adaptation solutions and programs across Europe.

This report describes the motivation, methods, development, and preliminary results of an empirical study about the acceptance of adaptation programs among European residents. The study seeks to elicit public preferences through a discrete choice experiment (DCE), wherein respondents are asked to choose between different programs, each characterised by a set of characteristics (or attributes), including the cost born by the public. Based on respondents' choices among different options, their willingness-to-pay (WTP) for a specific program can be estimated.

A survey was conducted among 9072 respondents in six European countries (over 1500 per country). It was deployed by the survey company Dynata using Computer Assisted Web Interviewing (CAWI) procedures. From these responses, we were able to derive WTP estimates both for the overall sample and for each of the six countries, and for sectors and resources. We found that income and education to have a significant, positive effect on the WTPs computed for the overall sample, but not for country-level WTPs. This is enough to allow the benefit transfer exercise described in deliverable D6.2.

The next section (Section 2.0) provides a brief review of the literature on DCEs with a particular focus on the (few) applications to climate change adaptation measures. The rest of this report describes how the study has been designed, developed and performed and the econometric approach applied, (Section 3.0), the dataset gathered (Section 4.0), the results (Section 5.0) and the conclusions (Section 6.0) of the study. The final version of the survey questionnaire is included in this deliverable as Annex 1, and Annex 2 reports on the details of the preliminary tests of our questionnaire.

2.0 LITERATURE REVIEW

Discrete Choice Experiments (DCEs) have become a standard econometric technique to address a wide range of policy concerns in transport economics (Caussade et al. 2005), environmental economics (Hanley et al. 2001), and health economics (de Bekker-Grob et al. 2012). DCEs have also been applied to climate policy, mostly to mitigation of climate change. These studies aim to elicit the willingness-to-pay (WTP) for cutting greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions, (Alberini et al. 2018; Scasny et al. 2017) or to elicit preferences towards specific features of climate policies and plans (Carson, Louviere and Wei, 2010). Alberini et al., looking at Italian and Czech households find a WTP per ton of CO₂ emissions avoided of EUR 133 in Italy and EUR 94 in the Czech Republic; they also find considerable heterogeneity within each country across income quantiles. Scasny et al. frame their DCE experiment in terms of targets (40% or 80% GHG emissions reductions), finding much lower values in Czech Republic, UK and Poland, ranging from EUR 45 in the UK to zero in Poland, again with high heterogeneity in WTP within each country. The approach taken by Carson, Louviere and Wei bears some methodological similarities to ours: they too are interested in estimating how different alternative policy bundles (in their case aimed at defining an Australian carbon tax) are evaluated by residents: they find significant heterogeneity in WTP depending on income and age, but on average Australians prefer a policy package that starts as early as possible, redistributes revenues to R&D funding and to cutting value added taxes (rather than helping low income households), and that excludes the transport but does not exempt energy intensive sectors.

The literature on the application of DCEs to adaptation is scarcer compared to the one on mitigation and mainly focuses on agricultural adaptation and coastal adaptation. DCE studies that address adaptation to climate change mostly refer to local study sites. Studies that address adaptation to climate change in agriculture often focus on specific local measures (for instance Nathambi, Morkova-Nevova and Wätzold, 2021 for irrigation water supply in Kenya; Schaafsma, Ferrini and Turner, 2019, for Malawi; Alcon et al., 2014, for Spain); a few cover preferences for more general adaptation solutions such as insurance against extreme weather events (Doherty et al., 2021 for Ireland; Jørgensen, Termansen, and Pascual, 2020 for Denmark; Furuka, Omori and Aizaki, 2021 for Myanmar); adoption of climate-resistant crop varieties (Waldman and Richardson, 2018, for Mali; Arora, Bansai and Ward 2019 for India) or land use changes (Pröbstl-Haider et al., 2016 for Austria). Some of these studies have a European focus: the latter study (Pröbstl-Haider et al., 2016) shows that Austrian farmers along the country's eastern borders, are mainly focused on fast-rotating, high productive crops that maximise farm profitability, and therefore not very much prepared to accept to switch to more sustainable crops or farming practices such as slower crop rotation. This tendency is reinforced if climate change brings about productivity increases, as it is projected for some crops grown in central Europe. Alcon et al. (2014) look at water supply for irrigation in water-scarcity-prone areas of Southern Spain, finding that farmers are willing to pay double the market price per cubic meter to increase the reliability of water supply, but have a strict preference for adaptation measures they are more familiar with (such inter-basin water transfers and the use of reclaimed water), as compared to water markets, stricter control over groundwater extraction and the adoption of Deficit irrigation techniques.

(Doherty et al., (2021), evaluate the attitudes of Irish farmers towards for multi-annual, weather-indexed, EU-supported insurance contracts for protection from extreme weather event compared to traditional farm insurance. Results show that the majority of farmers in the sample are willing to subscribe such contracts, and this holds particularly among younger farmers, farmers who holding farm insurance, farmers from the Border, Midlands and West regions, and farmers who experienced extreme weather events on the past.

An analogous study about Danish farmers (Jørgensen, Termansen, and Pascual, 2020) shows that there is interest in Denmark for innovative insurance against extreme weather events, particularly among farmers who grow their crops on low-productivity soils and, as it was the case in Ireland, have already experienced extreme weather in the past. This study (Jørgensen, Termansen, and Pascual, 2020) is also one of the few looking at bundles of adaptation measures, as it evaluates the possibility of applying jointly two adaptation solutions (weather insurance and improved land management), finding that farmers evaluate positively the bundle. Other studies looking at bundles of adaptation measures focus on areas outside Europe: Khanal et al. (2018) elicit preferences of Nepalese farmers for composite adaptation programs that include increased access to climate adaptive crop species and varieties, improved soil quality and irrigation and training in climate adaptive farming. Bro et al. (2020) look at the adoption of climate-resistant coffee varieties coupled with crop management practices in Nicaragua, finding that farmers are willing to introduce these measures.

Studies addressing adaptation to climate change in coastal areas focus on either single (e.g. Dachary-Bernard, Rey-Valette, and Rulleau 2018; Liski, Koetse, and Metzger 2019) or sets of adaptation measures (e.g. Remoundou et al. 2015; Chen, Swallow, and Yue 2020; Oliveira and Pinto 2020, Meyerhoff, Redhanz and Wunsch 2021; Wunsch Meyerhoff and Redhanz 2022). Liski, Koetse, and Metzger (2019) study how exposing respondents to additional knowledge about adaptation measures and for Scotland's Inner Forth Estuary can influence their WTP for adaptation, finding that providing extra knowledge has the double effect of increasing the preference for adaptation action over the status quo, and recalibrating WTP towards lower values (both effects of gaining more familiarity with the details of the measures, according to the authors). Dachary-Bernard, Rey-Valette, and Rulleau (2019) looking at adaptation to coastal erosion, investigate preferences of both coastal and hinterland residents for alternative modalities of relocation schemes (time, magnitude, and population consultation process) based on latent classes of risk perception, around Béziers, on the French Mediterranean coast. They find that respondents convene on the preferability of concerted relocation policies, and of step-by-step relocation implemented in 15–30 years' time; differences across latent classes show up in terms of the monetary attribute: there is a group that would like to see costs reduced, and hence has a significantly lower WTP than the average, and a class of people that are willing to pay significantly more. These classes can be characterised in terms of flooding risk perception, the second class being the one expressing the highest concerns about experiencing a major flood in the future.

As to studies about sets of measures in coastal areas, Remoundou et al. (2015) investigate preferences for preserving the environmental and recreational features of beaches in the Santander Bay area, Spain, through beach nourishment and measures to mitigate the negative consequences of jellyfish blooming, including closing beaches for up to 10 days a year. They find that respondents support all proposed measures. Chen, Swallow, and Yue (2020) compare preferences for conventionally engineered seawalls and nature-based protections designated as a living shoreline for inhabitants of Virginia's Eastern Shore, USA. Their WTP for coastal climate adaptation ranges from about USD 50 to USD 170 per year for five years. Regarding the coastal plan attributes, they find that the alternative management plan (living shoreline) is preferred to the traditional seawall by the Eastern Shore residents who evaluated trade-offs, and the ecosystem services bundled with the coastal plans have considerable but heterogeneous importance in Eastern Shore residents' considerations. Landry, Shonkwiler, and Whitehead (2020) investigate coastal erosion management preferences for North Carolina beaches in the United States. Oliveira and Pinto (2020) study consumers' choices for coastal erosion management alternatives at Praia da Amorosa in northern Portugal and find that respondents have a strong preference for adaptation measures over the status quo and for lighter and

nature-based interventions over heavy infrastructural interventions. Meyerhoff, Redhanz, and Wunsch (2021) investigate the trade-offs people are prepared to make in terms of coastal adaptation along the German coast in terms of six attributes: the extent of beach nourishment, dyke elevation, cliff protection, access to dunes, dyke and dunes realignment, and cost in terms of a coastal protection tax. Respondents could be sorted among three latent groups: those who desire major adjustments, those who are only ready to pay for a dike height increase, and those who are hesitant to bear higher costs. Overall, estimated aggregated WTP values turn out to be rather high, particularly those for adaptation scenarios preserving recreation activities, followed by those that protecting nature and safety. In a follow-up study (Wunsch, Meyerhoff and Redhanz 2022), the same authors argue that preferences for coastal adaptation in Germany remain quite stable in terms of heterogeneity patterns, despite the COVID-19 pandemic, although the relative size of the classes was significantly affected.

A couple of recent studies look at urban adaptation in Europe. Van Oijstaeijen et al. (2022) look at adaptation in Flemish municipalities in Belgium, exploring the attitudes of local authorities towards building a fictitious green area to provide recreation opportunities and natural cooling against summer heat as well as acting as a carbon sink. They find that impeding factors likely to reduce the participation into such project depend on the size of the municipality: larger municipalities need to deal with preexisting priorities while lacking the necessary knowledge affects more the smaller municipalities. The availability of financial resources appears to be also a crucial factor in determining the willingness to invest in urban green infrastructure.

Welling et al. (2022) look at the WTP for increasing green spaces in the city of Bremen, Germany as a measure to contrast extreme heat, finding positive and significant WTPs for all urban greening measures, and that these WTPs increases when respondents are provided extra information about the adaptation strategy these measures are part of. This study also investigates the relevance of believing that the opinions expressed by taking part in the survey will be duly considered by policymaker, finding that such belief does increase WTP, although the effect is not strongly significant for most measures. The environmental economics literature on DCE regards this phenomenon (dubbed “consequentiality”) as an important criterium for the credibility of the estimates. In our study, we have tested carefully its relevance for our WTP estimates (see Section 5.2).

3.0 METHODOLOGICAL APPROACH

We assess the degree of acceptance of adaptation policy measures by European residents using a Discrete Choice Experiment (DCE). DCEs provide quantitative information on the relative importance of various characteristics of a good, service, or policy that influence choices, and the trade-offs respondents are willing to make.

In a DCE, individual decisions about the object of the choice are determined by its characteristics, or attributes. One of these attributes is usually the price of the good or service, or the cost of the policy to the respondent (in the form of taxes or higher prices of certain products). Each attribute is made up of several levels that represent the degree or value that each attribute can take.

DCEs are based on data collected by asking survey respondents to indicate which they prefer among a number of scenarios ($N \geq 2$) described by attributes. In many cases, one of these policy options is the status quo or an opt-out option.

Some economists are critical of DCEs because they are sceptical of stated preference methods in general, due to the hypothetical nature of the scenarios and the fact that no actual transaction takes place. Respondents may for example overstate their willingness-to-pay (WTP). This issue is known in the literature as hypothetical bias¹, and calls for caution in implementing policy actions based on findings of DCE, and for putting in place other mitigation strategies. Policies implementing DCE studies should validate DCE findings through subsequent monitoring and ex-post policy assessment. Strategies to reduce hypothetical bias in DCEs (Colombo et al., 2020) can be divided into ex-ante and ex-post mitigation strategies. Ex-ante mitigation strategies seek to reduce hypothetical bias in the design stage of the survey by emphasising consequentiality (i.e., the consequence of the respondent's choices). This can be addressed by informing respondents that results will have an impact on policy (when this is the case), or through reminders to behave as they normally would behave - by including e.g. 'cheap talk' scripts (Doyon et al., 2015). Ex-post approaches to tackle hypothetical bias could include screening data for implausible responses based on post-experimental questions related to respondents' maximum WTP, for example, or respondents' stated certainty about a choice. In our DCE, we implement both ex-ante (by means of explanatory and chap talk texts, and by closing the questionnaire with a consequentiality question) and ex-post mitigation strategies (by carefully testing the implications of consequentiality for our results, see Section 5.0). Another option, not pursued in our study, is to combine stated preferences data with revealed preference data (Colombo et al., 2020).

In practical terms stated preference methods may have an edge over revealed preference methods (where actual behaviour is observed) when testing out new ideas and policies that do not exist yet, and, therefore, for which revealed preferences data are not available (Haab et al., 2020; Johnston et al., 2017).

To implement our DCE, we follow a series of essential steps (see Johnston et al., 2017; Mariel et al., 2021):

- Identification of the population targeted by the survey, and of the strategy to sample it (including sample size).
- Identification of attributes and realistic attribute levels (typically based on a literature review and stakeholder consultation, including interviews and focus group discussions).

¹ Hypothetical bias refers to individuals reporting unrealistic choices, behaviors or values within surveys or experimental studies, in the sense that what respondent state that they would do hypothetically, may differ from what they would actually do in real life (Buckell et al, 2020).

- Scenario development (including the decision to include a status-quo or opt-out option) and presentation in unambiguous language.
- Development and administration of the survey (data collection).
- Data cleaning and formatting for analysis.
- Analysis and interpretation.

3.1 Theoretical approach for Discrete Choice Experiments

In a DCE, it is posited that responses are driven by the Random Utility Model (McFadden, 1974), where the indirect utility \bar{V} from an alternative depends on the attributes of that alternative. The attributes may also appeal to a different extent to different individuals. In the random utility model, the indirect utility \bar{V} is made up of a deterministic component and a random component. Formally, we assume that the deterministic part is, for each adaptation solution j and respondent i :

$$(1) \quad \bar{V}_{ij} = \alpha \mathbf{X}_i + \beta(y - COST_{ij}) + \gamma \mathbf{XZ}_j$$

where the vector of variables \mathbf{X}_i is the set of the respondent i 's household characteristics; the vector of variables \mathbf{Z}_j is the set of characteristics of the policy package in alternative j ; y is the respondent's household income and $COST_{ij}$ is the cost of the program to the respondent's household (EUR /year). In equation (1), the α 's and γ 's are, respectively, the marginal utilities for households' characteristics and for policy packages' characteristics, and β is the marginal utility of income. Note that including income among explanatory variables is what allows estimating the monetary value for the attributes of interest, as explained below.

In this framework, individuals are assumed to choose between J alternatives, opting for the one associated with the highest utility (benefit or satisfaction). Thus, individual i will choose option k over h if and only if i attains a higher level of utility under k than under h .

On appending an error term (as the utility function is supposed to be stochastic - "random "-in this setting) ε (and dropping the respondents' index for brevity), the utility of option j becomes:

$$(2) \quad V_j = \alpha \mathbf{X}_i + \beta(y - COST_j) + \gamma \mathbf{XZ}_j + \varepsilon_j = \bar{V}_j + \varepsilon_j$$

The probability of choosing solution k over solution h is then:

$$(3) \quad \Pr(V_k > V_h) = \Pr(\bar{V}_k + \varepsilon_k > \bar{V}_h + \varepsilon_h)$$

Assuming that ε is distributed according to a cumulative standard logistic distribution probability function (log-normal for short) results in a logit econometric model, while assuming that its distribution is a cumulative normal, results in a probit model. The WTP for each component j of the policy package is $\hat{\alpha}_j / \hat{\beta}$ is, where the "hats" denote the maximum likelihood estimates. The coefficients (α and γ) thus generated can be used to determine whether the attributes are relevant (statistically significant), the direction of their relevance (shown by their algebraic sign) and their relative importance.

3.2 The questionnaire design

Designing the questionnaire for our survey took a considerable amount of creative effort, and a long trial-and-error process coupled with rigorous testing, due to the lack of suitable precursory studies in the literature. We went through four main stages:

- **An initial scoping stage** in which we identified the target population and the main topics of interest for our analysis, based on the goals of the project and features of the Demonstrator cases in

TransformAr. A questionnaire was distributed to the demonstrators to gather information needed for this initial scoping stage, and a workshop was conducted to discuss these topics in more detail directly with the relevant partners.

- **An early development stage** in which we outlined the main structure of the questionnaire and explored various alternatives for the questions and the features of the DCE experiment. We asked the partners in the demonstrator countries for their feedback about early drafts of the questionnaire. Furthermore, preliminary versions of the questionnaire were tested using ten one-on-one tests, which were conversation lasting one to two hours with lay respondents residing in Italy to fine tune-the order and the wording of questions and explanatory texts, and to identify a realistic range for the cost attribute.
- **An advanced development stage** in which the lesson learnt from the partners' comments and the first round of one-ones were incorporated in the draft questionnaire. The revised questionnaire was tested again by means of ten further one-on-one tests, carried out in Italy, Spain, Finland, the UK, and Norway.
- **A final stage** whereby the lessons learnt in the second round of tests were incorporated into the questionnaire, the final polishing touches were added and the final translations into Italian, Spanish, Finnish, Greek and Norwegian were carried out.

We describe below in more detail the main developments that took place during each of these stages.

3.3.1 Scoping Stage

This stage involved the following actions:

- Framing the problem: based on the main traits of the demonstrator adaptation solutions, identifying the features of adaptation measures that we wanted the DCE to capture.
- Identifying the themes to be covered by the other sections of the questionnaire,
- Identifying the target population to be sampled, in terms of the residents of which countries our respondents will be recruited.
- Identifying the relevant aspects of climate change adaptation, in terms of the attitudes of European residents. We also needed to identify which other aspects of their life are likely to matter for their attitudes towards adaptation to climate change.

To guide us in this scoping process, we sought the advice of the demonstrator case partners (ADEME, CETMAR, EGALÉO, LAPPERALANTA, MEDSEA AND WRT) through a short questionnaire, circulated in winter 2021-22. The main takeaway from this exercise was to narrow down the focus of the DCE on sectors targeted by adaptation actions implemented at demonstrator sites namely water, agriculture, and fisheries and to include nature-based solutions.

Also this stage, it was decided to include Norway (replicator demonstrator) in our sample instead of France, because the overseas location of the demonstrator raised concerns about the representativeness of responses for the whole France².

²In the case of France, the adaptation actions at the demonstrator site are specific to an overseas territory, Guadeloupe, and would not make sense in European France, because these actions' focus is precisely on overcoming the financial difficulties typical of an overseas territory of an EU country. This led to a dilemma about the relevant population to target with our survey in the case of France: either the entire national territory is covered, with the need of deploying the survey both in metropolitan France and in French

3.3.2 Early development stage

Drawing on the information collected from demonstrator partners, we set up to design the survey questionnaire. We wanted it to include a general part on the knowledge and attitudes of respondents about climate change and climate change adaptation, a core DCE section (in a standard setting, with two alternatives compared to status quo) and a concluding socio-demographic section.

The main challenge was to identify the relevant topics to be explored and the clearest language to be used in the questions and in the explanatory text boxes, to convey the right meaning to the respondents, while minimising the risk of fatigue. Some potentially relevant aspects of policy actions or fields for policy actions (financial measures, health adaptation; urban vs. rural adaptation, adaptation in wetlands, the institutions in charge of implementing the measures) had to be dropped from our attribute list in the interest of conciseness. Some of the discarded categories were included in broader categories: for instance, adaption measures targeting wetlands were included in the nature-based solutions.

By end July 2022 we arrived at a version that was deemed suitable for testing. Before launching the one-on-one tests with administrative employees at CMCC, we also sought feedback from partners in the survey countries. The main recommendation we gathered from this exercise, beside simplifying the language and adjusting the time for completion was to include questions on psychological distance³, competence and trust in the various agents involved, personal involvement, social norms, and qualitative evaluation of the proposed adaptive measures. We did include the consideration of trust, personal involvement, and competence in the phrasing of our questions about the attitudes of respondents towards climate change impacts and adaptation.

3.3.3 Improving the questionnaire building on one-on one tests.

We tested our questionnaire in two waves, with 22 tests respondents in total. The first wave was carried out in August 2022 with ten CMCC staff members in Italy: as we sought the point of view of lay persons, we recruited test respondents only among within the administrative staff. The second round of tests, carried out between February and early March 2023, was conducted with twelve lay persons from the public recruited

overseas territories; or only overseas territories are targeted. Both options are problematic. If the whole of France is surveyed, it will mostly represent the preferences and attitudes of people living in (geographical) Europe, the vast majority of which will not have ever visited any overseas territory, and hence respondents would likely feel quite distant from the adaptation needs in oversea territories and to have a limited knowledge thereof. Deploying the survey only in Guadeloupe and similar overseas territories would have been logistically complicated (due to the limited possibility of distributing a CAWI-based survey) and would produce results hardly comparable with those derived based on the responses of a (geographically) European sample, as it would overrepresent the view of people living in overseas territories. It was thus decided to leave France aside for this DCE.

³ “Psychological distance” is a psychological construct used to explain how people perceive objects and events as concrete or abstract, and hence more or less relevant to them. It is a well-known explanatory factor in behavioral studies about attitudes towards climate change, where it is used to explain the degree of commitment to engage in mitigation and adaptation: public perception of climate change as abstract and distant may undermine climate action (Maiella et al., 2020).

within residents of Italy, Spain, Finland, the UK and Norway. To guarantee incentive compatibility⁴, each test participant was rewarded with a EUR 50 compensation. We summarise here our main findings from these tests, while more details can be found in Annex 2.

The first round of tests aimed at finding out whether people were at their ease with questions about climate impacts, adaptation policies and measures, and with participating in a DCE.

The second round of tests, following a similar protocol as the first round, put new elements to test, among which, two key ones are worth highlighting here. First, we tested whether the use of a “referendum” format could help making the DCE exercise easier for the respondents. Differently from the standard DCE format (whereby two alternatives are compared to the status quo), in a referendum format DCE just one policy package is compared to the status quo. Secondly, we also tested attitudes towards the time dimension of costs and benefits of adaptation: we checked whether annual instalments for several years (ten years in our case) were preferable to one lump-sum payment, whereby the funds thus collected would be earmarked to finance the policy measure during the subsequent ten years. We also asked whether having to wait for a measure to be operative or knowing that some measure may come with an expiry date, would have been a problem.

Overall, participants in both rounds of one-on-one tests found the information material clear and interesting. Some minor clarifications were required in the second round, in terms of finding plain language equivalents for some technical terms.

The DCE example of the first round was in general found clear, but the cost attribute needed clarification – if annual, the number of years was often indicated as a crucial piece of information to be specified.

More useful details on the DCE emerged during the second round. An important concern raised by one of the respondents in this round was related to strategic behaviour in the DCE exercise: people may vote for a policy package if presented as the only one available, but they may actually prefer a different configuration, based on what they learnt from the explanatory material provide earlier in the questionnaire. If multiple referendum choice cards are proposed, people might vote against a package if they hope to get a better deal in the subsequent runs or vote in favour of a packages even though their preferred configuration did not show up, for fear of be left empty-handed. These considerations prompted us to seek a refined way to present the rules of the game of the referendum format.

The DCE exercise of the second round made clear that the referendum format was well understood. However, relatively low values of the cost attribute always resulted in a vote for the program. When we increased it, people started to vote against the program for costs higher than EUR 100-800 per year, depending on their country of residence and their income.

The time dimension was deemed important but so was the opportunity to have long-lasting adaptation solutions in place: people are prepared to wait to see the results of adaptation actions and to contribute to their implementation through a reasonable increase in their tax bill.

All test respondents in the second round of tests considered an additional annual income tax to be paid each year for ten years as the most viable means of payment in their country, rather than a comparable lump sum payment used to finance policy action in the next decade. This has important consequences for the survey design and the econometric model and implies that a simplified setting without intertemporal dependence (and hence without non-linearities) can be adopted.

⁴ It is standard practice to reward test participants. People may agree to an interview on a voluntary basis, but only a non-negligible reward ensures their full attention.

3.3.4 The final questionnaire

Based on the lessons learnt from the second round of tests, we finalised our English version of the questionnaire and translated it in the other five languages. The final version of the questionnaire is included in Annex 1.

The final questionnaire includes seven sections. After a few demographic questions needed to verify the sampling quotas, the focus progressively narrows from broad attitudes towards climate change to the more specific features of adaptation policies, followed by the DCE. The final section deals again with the socio-demographic features of the respondent's household. Along the questionnaire, we provide essential information about climate change impacts and adaptation to the respondents in, we hope, a clear and neutral way. Importantly, this information can be retrieved by the respondents at any time during the completion of the questionnaire by clicking on clearly visible links placed in the sides of the screen. The questionnaire closes with a final question about whether respondents deem it likely that policy makers will take the results of this survey into consideration when designing future adaptation policies. More specifically, the questionnaire includes the following sections:

Section 0. Sampling quota questions: Basic sociodemographic questions to check sample stratification at the national level. We wanted to make sure that key features of the population in the six countries of our analysis are captured by our sample. We asked people about their gender, education and income (expressed as income brackets) because we wanted national sub-samples to fit the sampling quotas we deemed realistic and relevant for our study (see Section 3.3 for details).

Finally, we asked information about where people lived (through their postal code and their assessment of the urbanization degree of their area of residence) to generate a “distance from the coast” variable, defined as the minimum distance from the coast of the centroid of the postal code area of each respondent. and to provide an alternative source of information for the degree of urbanization variable (which is not available for the UK).

Section A. Climate change knowledge and concern: After a brief information box on climate change causes and impacts, respondents were asked about their familiarity with the consequences of climate change, their personal concern about them, and their rating of specific climate risks in the country where they lived.

Section B. Adaptation. After a brief information box about the concept of adaptation and which kind of actions can be undertaken by public authorities to put in place climate change adaptation measures, this section explored respondents' familiarity with adaptation, by asking which sectors in their country stands better chances to adapt. The focus of the questionnaire then narrowed down on the features of the adaptation actions to be evaluated in the DCE, (Table 3-1) and asks about the familiarity of respondents with such adaptation solutions.

Table 3-1. Summary description of adaptation measures in the questionnaire

Area of concern	Climate change risks	Examples of adaptation measures
<p>Water supply for drinking and all other residential, commercial, and industrial uses.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Droughts - Saltwater intrusion - Water scarcity 	<p><i>Infrastructure Measures</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Organize water storage (in reservoirs) - Build desalination plants <p><i>Institutional Measures</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Import water from other locations - Establish and coordinate water rights markets <p><i>Nature-based* Measures</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Restore wetlands to help recharge aquifers.
<p>Rivers and water bodies (lakes, lagoons, etc.)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Higher water temperatures are bad for certain species -Floods and runoff during extreme weather events deposit sediments, and worsen water quality - Floods cause damage to people and property - Floods may destroy or damage bridges, and infrastructure 	<p><i>Infrastructure Measures</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Raise riverbanks - Reinforce infrastructure (bridges, etc.) <p><i>Institutional Measures</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Improve early warning systems for extreme events - Technical standards for new and existing infrastructure to ensure it is resilient to climate change <p><i>Nature-based* Measures</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Use plants and wetlands to limit runoff and help maintain water quality
<p>Coastal areas</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Coastal flooding 	<p><i>Infrastructure Measures</i></p>

- Sea level rise

- Build or install barriers / floating barriers
- Restore beaches
- Strengthen existing infrastructure

Institutional Measures

- Technical standards for new and existing infrastructure to ensure it is resilient to climate change
- Early warning systems for extreme events

Nature-based Measures*

- Dunes, beach nourishment, wetlands.
- Coral banks and mussels have been found to mitigate sea level rise and coastal erosion.

- Loss of crops due to drought, changed temperature and precipitation patterns

Agriculture

- This may affect high-value crops (e.g., certain wine grapes)

Infrastructure Measures

- More efficient irrigation systems (e.g., drip irrigation instead of sprinkling)
- Strengthen irrigation networks

Institutional Measures

- Plans and regulations for land use to better cope with climate change

Nature-based Measures*

- Climate-resistant crops
- Climate-resistant breeds of livestock

Forests

- Increased risk of wildfires

Infrastructure Measures

- Some species of plants may be heavily affected n.a.
- Increased spread of harmful, invasive species of plants and insects that may damage forests

Institutional Measures

- Strengthen fire prevention systems
- Monitor species of plants and insects, and prompt eradication of harmful, invasive plants and insects

Nature-based Measures*

- Sustainable forest management practices

- Species will be affected by climate change
- Marine fisheries and aquaculture are expected to be at higher risk than freshwater aquaculture n.a.
- Impacts will be different across Europe

Infrastructure Measures

Fisheries and aquaculture (fish and seafood farming)

Institutional Measures

- Adjust catch quotas to changes in fish population induced by climate change
- Monitoring of environment and fish health
- Promote new technologies, breeding and feeding programs

Nature-based Measures*

- Climate-resistant breeds

Section C. Benefits of adaptation and **Section D. Cost of adaptation** are short sections containing only one question each. Section C enquires about which societal groups or institutions, in the opinion of the respondents, benefit the most from the implementation of a selection of adaptation measures. Section D

asks which groups or institutions the respondents deem likely to bear the costs of implementing such measures. Section D also offers a brief explanation about the economic concept of cost, clarifying that it can be monetary or non-monetary (i.e., personal discomfort from performing an action).

Section E. Adaptation policies is the core section of the questionnaire, where the DCE takes place. It opens with an explanation about the policy package depiction used in the experiment, the way the experiment works, and then respondents are presented with the DCE, described in detail in Section 3.3.

Finally, **Section F. Demographics** closes the questionnaire with questions about further characteristics of the respondents' households, such as the employment status of the respondent and the age composition of the household. We check whether household members work in sectors directly affected by the adaptation packages considered in this survey, or they are likely to be involved in the policy process as employees of local or national authorities in charge of adaptation policies.

The questionnaire closes with a final question about **consequentiality**, that is the perceived relevance of the information collected through this experiment for future policy action⁵. Specifically, we ask our respondents how likely it is, in their view, that the opinions they reported in this survey and those of other consumers will be duly considered by policymakers and authorities in their country, ranking this on a scale from 1 to 5, where 1=not likely at all and 5=very likely.

3.3 The experimental design

We set up our DCE to be:

- understandable for the respondent;
- computationally manageable;
- able to capture the features of interest of adaptation policy packages;
- able to generate a menu of choice packages which are both realistic and cover reasonably well the spectrum of possible combinations;
- generating a database likely to provide answers to our research questions.

First, we wanted our sample to be representative of each country's population, while capturing some features that we consider key for our study. We wanted our national samples to have:

- Equal gender shares (50-50) among the respondents who agreed to reveal their gender;
- Education quotas capturing those of the population in the respective countries, for lower secondary education⁶, upper secondary and upper secondary non-tertiary education, and for tertiary education – according to the OECD-ISCED system);

⁵ Consequentiality can be defined, in a policy perspective, as the positive probability that policy action will be influenced by policy response, perceived by the respondent (Johnston et al., 2017). Concern for consequentiality is linked to the concern for the hypothetical bias and has been a persistent theme in the debate about state preference studies (Carson et al., 2014). Checking for consequentiality is currently recommended for stated preference studies (Johnston et al., 2017).

⁶ While most education systems across Europe share the same broad path, from the primary schools to Ph.D., curricula differ substantially in terms of duration, structure of vocational/professional education compared to high-school and university curricula and labelling of educational attainments. Also, school systems have evolved through the years, resulting in equivalent attainments labelled differently across generations within

- 50% of the respondents with household income below the median household income for that country, and 50% above the median household income for that country (in terms of after-tax disposable household income)⁷.

The adherence to these quotas in our final sample is ensured by the initial screening questions in the questionnaire.

We applied three **split sample treatments**, all independent (orthogonal) from each other: one on the geographical coverage of the policy programs evaluated in the DCE, one on their ability to reduce the damages caused by climate change, and one the specific labelling of a class of adaptation measures. Thus, we used the first two split sample treatments to understand whether the higher or lower degree of protection from climate change damages, or a higher or lower geographical coverage of the measures, matter in the decision to support a given policy package. These two treatments appear as attributes within the choice cards, but they are fixed at one of their two possible values for each half of the sample. Moreover, being mindful of the importance of language in purporting the characteristics of alternatives in a choice experiment, we used the third split sample treatment to test whether the connection with nature of certain policy measures triggers more positive attitudes towards such measures. Therefore people will be split into subsamples as follows⁸, with each subsample including exactly half of each national sample:

- half of our sample in each country is always being offered programs with high geographical coverage of the damages (80% of the national territory), while the other half is always offered a lower geographical coverage (60% of the national territory);
- half of our sample in each country is always being offered programs bringing about a large drop in climate damages (75% damage reduction) while the other half is always offered a smaller percentage reduction in climate damages (50% damage reduction);

the same country. The Bologna Process has brought some uniformity across the EU, but only for students graduated after the years 1999-2006 (when this process became effective in most EU member countries). To account for this situation in our questionnaire, we used the OECD-ISCED system (OECD/Eurostat/UNESCO Institute for Statistics, 2015), whereby education levels are classified in nine levels ranging from 0 (no education or primary school not completed) to 8 (Ph.D.), and sorted the most common names (expressed in the national language of the countries in our sample) for all types of education attainments available, now and in the past, across the OECD-ISCED levels. We dropped level 0 because we think it highly implausible to find a non-negligible number of respondents without any education able to interact with a CAWI questionnaire.

⁷ We inquired about income classes instead of exact income amounts to minimise the number of protest answers from people who may feel that income is sensitive personal information. We used a reasonably wide list of possible monthly household income classes, with enough options along the whole spectrum of the income distributions in our six countries, This is not straightforward in our sample, because of the wide disparity between higher income countries such as Norway (and, to a lesser extent, Finland and the UK) and lower income countries such as Greece (and to a lesser extent, Spain and Italy). For instance, households in the second lowest decile in Norway have already an income higher than households in the ninth decile in Greece, according to Eurostat income distribution data. Thus, our brackets span from “up to EUR 500” to “over 12.500” EUR/month. Equivalent income classes for the UK and Norway were converted into the local currency using Purchasing Power Parity (PPP) and rounded for clarity.

⁸ The selection into each subsample is random and, for each split sample criterium, independent from the other two.

- half of our sample in each country is always reading about “nature-based” solutions throughout the whole questionnaire (and in particular is being offered programs mentioning “nature-based” solutions in the choice cards) while the other half will always see a more neutral wording such as “non-infrastructure measures”, that omits any reference to nature, throughout the questionnaire.

The attributes of the choice card.

Table 3-2 summarises the attributes shown in the choice cards and their possible levels. Besides the levels of geographical coverage and the damage reduction implementing split sample treatments⁹, our choice cards include information on the resources or sectors covered by the policy, the types of measures adopted within the package, the geographical coverage of the package, the reduction in climate change damages to be delivered by the policy and the cost of the program to the taxpayers who would face an additional income tax, to be paid each year for a total of 10 years.

Table 3-2 Attributes and their levels in the choice cards

Attribute	Levels
Water supply for drinking and all other residential, commercial and industrial uses	Covered/not covered
Surface waters (rivers, lakes, lagoons)	Covered/not covered
Coastal areas	Covered/not covered
Agriculture	Covered/not covered
Forests	Covered/not covered
Fisheries and aquaculture	Covered/not covered
Type of measure	Infrastructure/ Nature-based ¹⁰ / Regulation/ Infrastructure & Nature-based/ Infrastructure & Regulation/ Nature-based & Regulation/ Infrastructure & Nature-based & Regulation
Cost to each taxpayer	EUR 100/ 250/ 500/ 750/ 1000/ 1500 ¹¹

Figure 3.1 provides an example of choice card as shown in the CAWI.

The content of each policy package shown to each respondent, are determined by:

- assigning an attribute combination that specifies the sectors/resources targeted and the cost of the package, chosen randomly among the set of combinations specified in the experimental design of the survey;

⁹ Geographical coverage and climate change damage reduction are not listed in this table, because, although they are shown on the choice cards, they are not full-fledged attributes: each respondent never saw their level change across the seven cards.

¹⁰ Replaced with “Non-infrastructure” in half of the sample, to implement the third split sample treatment.

¹¹ To be paid each year for the next ten years. Replaced with equivalent amounts in local currency PPPs for the UK and Norway.

- the subsamples the respondent is assigned to by the split sample treatments, in terms of 1) labelling nature-based solutions as “nature-based” or “non-infrastructure”, 2) low or high geographical coverage and 3) low or high damage protection of the policy package.

Would you vote in favour or against program A? If a majority of voters approved program A, it would be implemented and it would deliver the benefits listed below. You, and every other household, would have to pay the sum listed below. If a majority votes against program A, the program would not be implemented, its benefits would not be experienced, and you and everyone else would pay nothing.

[Click here to see the intro again](#)

Pair 1 of 7

	Program A	NO Program A
Water supply for drinking and all other residential, commercial, and industrial uses		
Surface waters (rivers, lakes, lagoons)	Covered	
Coastal areas	Covered	
Agriculture	Covered	
Forests		The program would not be implemented, its benefits would not be experienced, and you and everyone else would pay nothing.
Fisheries and aquaculture		
Type of measure	nature-based solutions	
Geographical coverage	60%	
Climate change damages reduction	75%	
Cost to each taxpayer	£110 each year for the next 10 years	
	<input type="radio"/> in favour of program A	<input type="radio"/> against program A

Figure 3.1 Choice card example from the online survey

The Discrete Choice Experiment format. The referendum format implies that each of the seven-policy packages will be compared only to the status quo, and not with another policy package and the status quo, as in the most commonly used DCE format. In the status quo, no *new* adaptation policy is put in place, but no extra tax is levied on their income. We adopt a referendum format for our DCE because it is a way to reduce drastically the complexity of the experimental design, by dropping one of the two alternative policy programs and comparing the remaining one directly to the status quo. For the respondent, it is easier to answer to a few binary choice questions, rather than comparing three options the same number of times. The responses to a referendum format DCE can be interpreted as implying that the respondent’s WTP for the program is higher or lower than the cost of the program to the respondent.

Ultimately, our design includes **three split sample treatments** (one for the language used to express nature-based solutions, one for the damage reduction and on for the geographical coverage) **eight attributes** (the six resource/sectors, the measure applied and the cost attribute) with their respective **levels**, (whether a sector is covered or not, the three types of measures alone or in combination, and the six levels of additional taxes).

There are of course various possible specific measures of each kind for each resource/sector¹² which we do not include directly in the choice card. Instead, we provide examples of relevant infrastructure, nature-based and institutional measures for each resource/sector (if relevant) in the information material preceding the DCE (see Table 3-1), striving to keep the content of possible combinations clear and unambiguous. Thus, we make clear that “water supply” refers only to residential, commercial, and industrial uses, while “irrigation” is used only for infrastructure adaptation in agriculture; also, there are no infrastructure adaptation measures of any significance for public adaptation policies for fisheries and forests.

In our setting, the “real” attributes in the DCE (i.e., the elements in the choice cards not used for split sample treatments) are the six resource/sectors, the measures applied and the cost attribute. There are six resources/sectors that can be either covered or not covered by policy packages. There are eight theoretical ways in which policies or combinations of policies can be applied (including the one in which no measure is applied) and there are six different levels of costs for the taxpayers. The full range of all theoretically possible configurations is called the **full factorial** and counts 2^6 possible configurations for sectors/resources being covered or not covered, 8^1 configurations for the type of policies and 6^1 for the costs. Thus, the full factorial has $2^6 \times 8^1 \times 6^1 = 3072$ combinations. Our relatively large sample of 1500 respondents in each country, each one facing seven choice cards, implies that on average each possible combination can be seen almost 3.5 times in each country.

Following Carson, Louviere and Wei (2010), who have a similar setting in terms of eliciting preferences for policy packages, we note that we do not need to use the full factorial design but we can select a subset of the above-specified combinations that guarantees a good coverage of individual sectors and type of measures across the seven choice cards while avoiding repetitions of packages across the cards seen by each respondent, and avoiding irrelevant combinations. Considering that our sample size is relatively large, we have implemented a strategy that chooses a subset of the 3072 full-factorial alternatives, granted this subset provides enough variation in attributes to identify all parameters involved. To verify whether all parameters involved are identified, we have relied on a Monte Carlo simulation exercise. Accordingly, the first step consisted in defining a set of true parameters and using them in a data-generating process explaining the choice under analysis. The second step consisted in randomly choosing a subset of alternatives from the full factorial. The third step consisted in testing whether this subset of alternatives would identify the true parameters on a pseudo-population of respondents. Our final design includes a total of 224 alternatives, which we have divided in 32 sets including each seven alternatives. Each alternative/program reflects a combination of values of the attributes covering the sector/resource, (combination of) types of measure, and program cost, and assigned them at random to the respondents, along with one of the eight possible combinations of nature-based versus non-infrastructure measure denomination, geographical coverage, and reduction of climate change damages. Note that our final design requires the additional assumption that the same types of measures are to be applied uniformly across the sectors covered in the choice card.

We also use debriefing questions to get additional feedback on what the DCE meant to the respondent. After each referendum question, respondents are asked whether they deem that the package they just examined would bring about benefits only in terms of climate change adaptation, or it might have also co-benefits

¹² see Table 3-1 for some examples; note that for some resource/sectors, some types of measures may not be available.

related to environmental quality, biodiversity, human health, or other fields. Finally, we ask them to identify which aspects of the packages mattered the most, and which the least in determining their votes.

3.4 The econometric model

In our study, we posit that when answering each valuation question, the respondents compare their WTP for the program being considered with the cost they would have to incur if the program was adopted. They will pronounce themselves in favour of the program if their WTP exceeds the cost amount, and against it otherwise.

To depict the specification(s) of our econometric model in terms of the framework of Section 3.1, we assume that the respondent's WTP for any given program, which we do not observe, is equal to

$$(4) \quad WTP_{ijk}^* = \alpha + A_{ijk} + \varepsilon_{ijk}$$

where i denotes the respondent, j the version of the questionnaire, and k the choice card ($k=1, \dots, 7$). ε is an econometric error term, which we assume to be normally distributed with mean zero and variance σ^2 . In other words, the underlying WTP is normally distributed.

A_{ijk} is a shorthand for all our explanatory variables. More specifically, in our base specification, we define A_{ijk} as

$$(5) \quad A_{ijk} = \left(\sum_{l=1}^6 x_{ijkl} \delta_l + \sum_{m=1}^3 M_{ijkm} \gamma_m \right)$$

where x_l ($l=1, 2, \dots, 6$) denotes whether a specific sector (e.g., agriculture, water supply, etc.) is addressed by the program, and M_m denotes whether infrastructure, nature-based or institutional measures would be used.

The inclusion of an intercept in the right-hand side of (4) merits discussion. Parameter α is by definition the WTP when no sector is covered and no measure is used, which for all practical purposes means that there is no program, and thus captures the possibility that respondents may tend to choose the program no matter what. This “action bias” is thus the opposite of “inaction or inertia bias” (Tykocinski et al., 1985).

Our study follows a simplified DCE approach, whereby we adopt a referendum format, and each policy package is compared with the status quo. Hence two alternatives are compared in each round. Thus, if each respondent only examined one program *vis-à-vis* the status quo, the probability that they are in favour of the program is

$$(6) \quad Pr(\varepsilon_{ijk} \geq cost_{ijk} - \alpha - A_{ijk}) = \Phi\left(\frac{\alpha + A_{ijk}}{\sigma} - \frac{cost_{ijk}}{\sigma}\right)$$

where $\Phi(\cdot)$ is the cumulative distribution function (cdf) of the standard normal. Equation (7) plus its counterpart for a respondent who declines the program are the contributions to the likelihood function of a probit model.

We allow the ε terms to be correlated with the observed component of the respondent's WTP. This correlation allows for the presence of unobserved factors affecting the respondent's taste for the attributes under study. We, therefore, use the random effects probit model to address econometrically this assumed correlation.

We begin expanding A_{ijk} by fitting four random effects probit models—one for each of the four subsamples that were assigned a different combination of our scope variables, GEOLARGE and REDUCELARGE, where GEOLARGE is a dummy variable that takes on a value of one if the respondent was always assigned programs that would cover 80% of the national territory (zero if 60% of the national territory) and REDUCELARGE is a dummy equal to one when the respondent examines programs that reduce the damages from climate change

(in the indicated sectors) by 75% (zero if by 50%). Once these random effects probit models are fit by the method of maximum likelihood, we check whether the estimated coefficients on program attributes (sectors and measures) have the expected signs and are individually and jointly statistically significant. We then use the estimated parameters arising from the random effects probit specification and plug them in equation (4) to predict the WTP for i) coverage of individual sectors, and ii) for a “full” program that covers all sectors and deploys all measures for each of the four subsamples. We check whether they are statistically different across the subsamples—with the expectations that the WTP should be larger for more extensive geographical coverage and more pronounced reduction of the damages from climate change.

One concern with our study design is that the fact that we kept the geographical coverage and the size of the reduction of the climate change damages fixed within a respondent may compromise the responsiveness of the WTP to such features. Should we find that to be the case, we experiment with *imposing* on the estimation routine that the WTP is sensitive to external scope. We are especially interested in examining the consequences of forcing such responsiveness on the estimates of the *other* coefficients in the model.

Specifically, we pool the responses from all the four split samples, and, following equation (4), we assume that programs with 80% coverage of the national territory elicit WTP values that must be 80/60 those for programs with 60% coverage. This implies that the coefficients on the sectors and measures in the 80% coverage programs must be 4/3 of their counterparts from the subsample that was assigned the 60% coverage programs. Likewise, we assume that programs that reduce the damages from climate change by 75% elicit WTP values that are 75/50 those for programs that offer a 50% damage reduction. This means that the coefficients on the sectors and measures for programs that reduce damages by 75% must be $75/50=3/2$ their counterparts estimated from the subsample that receive 50% damage reduction programs. We impose these restrictions on the random effects probit and examine the consequences in terms of fit of the model, the estimated coefficients on the other attributes of the program and any other regressors, and the WTP for adaptation.

Whether or not we impose such restrictions on the coefficients, we further estimate variants of the model where term A_{ijk} in equation (5) is augmented with $\mathbf{z}_i\boldsymbol{\beta}$, where \mathbf{z} is a collection of socioeconomic characteristics of the respondents and/or attitudes towards climate change and adaptation. In principle we can include in A_{ijk} also other key **individual characteristics of the respondents we elicited through the questionnaire** likely to influence their attitude towards adaptation, such as their gender, education level, age, income, and the place where they live. Also, experience and qualitative opinions about adaptation elicited in the survey, may help explain the WTP for adaptation measures.

We also fit the random effects probit when the sample is limited to certain respondents—for example, those who appear to trust that their responses will be taken into account by the authorities, or those who exhibited a variety of yes/no votes for the program over the seven choice cards.

4.0 DATA

4.1 The dataset

The survey was ready for a preliminary soft launch at the end of August 2023. The first soft launch took place in September 2023 and highlighted the need to rescale the cost attribute. In particular, cost values were further fine-tuned to reflect the households' purchasing power differences across countries, while the three highest options were scaled down to reach a maximum at the purchasing power equivalent of EUR 1500. A second soft launch was implemented at the beginning of October 2023, shortly followed by the launch of the full survey on October 23rd, 2023. Adjustments after the second soft launch included some further polishing of the translations and, importantly, adding some further explanatory text before the DCE questions to make sure that the implications of the cost attribute on the households' budget were understood. Sampling targets were reached at different times across countries: while we were able to close the Italian, Spanish, British and Finnish surveys respectively on November 8th, November 10th, November 16th and November 21st, it took three more weeks to close the Greek and Norwegian ones, on December 15th.

Our survey was distributed by the survey company Dynata. Dynata is one of the leading survey companies worldwide, established 45 years ago, with a global proprietary panel of 70 million respondents (11 million in Europe) and over 100 million surveys completed so far, including surveys for academic research studies. Their long record of conducting surveys, their direct access to such a large number of respondents, and their proprietary tools and procedures to guarantee the highest quality of the data, were key assets in their selection - besides submitting the best value-for-the-money proposal.

Dynata implements a set of checks to optimise the quality of the data, starting with strict criteria for the selection of the panel members to proprietary procedures for data validation. A digital identity-validation technology maps respondents' credentials against key data points to eliminate duplicates and frauds in real time; in practice, real-time procedures are in place to make sure that respondents are really the persons they claim to be. During the administration of the survey, a proprietary algorithm (QualityScore™) checks respondents' attention by monitoring response patterns at every question to identify fraudulent behaviour and inattention, drawing on artificial intelligence to detect invalid answers. The idea is to drop from the final database only those respondents whose behaviour, during the completion of the questionnaire, highlighted that they were unlikely to be paying enough attention to the questions posed to them (either because they were too fast in answering or where repeatedly giving the same answer too many times or were likely untruthful in their answers) and thus discard only truly unacceptable responses. The algorithm is in any case always complemented by visual inspection by the Dynata team of the answers provided by the respondents. In total, 11.257 people were contacted for our survey, of which 9.072 completed the final questionnaire, while 2185 people were discarded during the administration of the questionnaire as a consequence of the aforementioned checks. Table 4-1 shows the reasons for questionnaire termination. The vast majority (68%) of the terminations was due to failing QualityScore™ checks, followed by those who spontaneously opted out from the survey after reading the introductory screen (22%) and those who gave inappropriate answers to open-ended questions (7%). The highest concentration of discarded questionnaires occurred in Greece, while Finnish responders gave the least reasons for termination.

Table 4-1. Breakout of terminated surveys by country and cause.

	Total	UK	GR	IT	ES	FI	NO
Prefers not to participate	494	110	43	36	72	72	161
Age below 18	37	7	3	9	7	2	9
QualityScore™ check failed	1.479	218	338	285	266	164	208
Disqualified: Bad open-ends	159	18	15	39	32	18	37
Disqualified: Other	16	0	6	0	0	0	10
Total	2.185	353	405	369	377	256	425

Descriptive statistics about sociodemographic features of the sample are displayed in Table 4-2. The sample meets the quotas spelled out in our sampling frame and is representative of sociodemographic conditions in the countries under scrutiny. Some national features are worth noting: countries are similar in terms of gender shares, average age of the respondents and household size, but they are different in terms of household income (households in our Norwegian sample can rely upon an income 2.75 times the one of Greek households), education (university-educated respondents in our Italian and Finnish samples are less than half those in UK, Norway and Greece) and presence of children or elders in the household: children under 18 are present in almost half the respondents' households in Spain and Greece compared to only in a quarter of Finnish households; conversely, Greek, Spanish and Finnish households are also those with the lowest presence of senior members. People residing on the coast prevail in Norway (70%) and Greece (54%), while they barely reach 21% of the sample in UK and Italy (where however there are quite high shares of respondents living within 5 and 50 km from the coast). The highest share of respondents living in the interior of the country is in Spain, almost half of the national sample, while only 6% of the respondents live in the interior of Greece and Norway. Our respondents tend to live in urban or semi-urban areas, with a share of the rural population that ranges from a bare 7% in Greece to 25% in Italy. Descriptive statistics about concern for climate change impacts among our respondents are displayed in Table 4-3. People seem to worry the most in Spain, followed closely by Greece and Italy, and worry the least in Norway and Finland. This pattern is in line with the severity of the impacts foreseen by climate science in these countries. Finally, the overall percentage of votes in favour of the policy packages proposed in the choice cards is over 50%, in all countries but Finland (where in any case majority is missed by a sheer 2%) and peaks at 60% in Spain.

Table 4-2 Descriptive Statistics of the Sample. Socio-demographic features.

	Spain	Greece	Italy	Finland	Norway	United Kingdom	All countries
Female respondents (%)	48	50	50	50	45	50	49
Age of the respondents (years)	44.96	41.67	47.94	47.42	46.52	52.87	46.88
Full-time employed (%)	54	51	43	39	47	44	46
Monthly household income (PPP Euro)	2580	1530	2460	3120	4210	3150	2830
College degree or post-graduate work (%)	36	42	19	23	46	51	36
Lower or intermediate education (%)	64	58	81	77	54	49	64
Household size (count)	2.98	2.86	2.77	2.08	2.48	2.46	2.61
At least one child under 18 at home (%)	45	42	30	26	35	30	35
At least one person 65 or older at home (%)	21	17	30	21	26	33	25
At least one household member working in sectors covered by the programs (%)	19	14	13	11	17	5	13
At least one household member working in the public sector (%)	8	6	7	5	8	4	6
Respondents living within 5 km of coast (%)	31	54	21	37	70	21	39
Respondents living 5-50 km from coast (%)	22	40	35	25	24	53	33
Respondents living in the interior of the country (%)	47	6	44	38	6	26	28

Respondents living in urban area (%)	59	66	38	33	40	28	44
Respondents living in suburbs or small towns (%)	28	27	37	50	38	53	39
Respondents living in rural areas (%)	13	7	25	17	22	19	17
Observations ¹³	10.668	10.402	10.318	10.241	10.094	10.297	62.020

Table 4-3 Descriptive Statistics of the Sample. Attitudes towards climate change impacts and adaptation programs.

	Spain	Greece	Italy	Finland	Norway	United Kingdom	All countries
Very concerned about rising sea levels (%)	46	40	43	26	24	43	37
Very concerned about damage to crops (%)	53	49	49	36	27	42	43
Very concerned about heat waves (%)	59	57	53	31	25	43	45
Very concerned about floods (%)	53	60	52	27	30	45	45
Very concerned about droughts (%)	65	49	54	34	25	39	45
Very concerned about extreme weather (%)	49	57	55	33	27	44	44
Very concerned about loss of species (%)	51	47	46	40	30	47	44
Very concerned about invasive species (%)	41	26	42	26	21	34	32
Very concerned about mass migrations (%)	38	36	36	32	25	37	34
Percentage votes in favour of the program	60	56	58	48	58	54	56

¹³ Our sample comprises 9072 respondents. However, our unit of observation is actually the vote cast for each choice card shown. Our total number of observations is thus the number of respondents times seven, the number of choice cards shown during the DCE. This generates 63504 observations. However, 212 respondents preferred not to answer to the income question, thus 212 x 7 = 1484 observations were dropped from the sample on which these descriptive statistics, that cover income, were computed.

Figure 4.1 plots the share of the respondents that opted for the program at each cost level. Just under 75% of the respondents declared themselves in favour of the programs at the lowest level of cost (EUR 100). The share of respondents in favour of the program falls as the cost of the program increases, exhibits a slight non-monotonicity between EUR 750 and EUR 1000, and remains above 40% at the highest cost level.

Figure 4.1 Share of total responses over all DCE performed, that were in favour of the program, by program cost amount

Table 4-4 Percentage votes for the program for the four split samples.

Geographic Coverage %	60	80	60	80
Damage Reduction %	50	50	75	75
Program Cost (EUR)				
100	73.06	71.08	73.03	71.52
250	65.20	66.91	65.18	67.45
500	54.87	54.17	54.38	55.37
750	49.72	46.11	48.44	48.63
1000	49.03	48.32	48.80	48.57
1500	44.65	43.29	44.67	42.36

Table 4-4 displays the shares of “in favour” votes by cost amount for each of the split samples that received one of the four combinations of geographical coverage and extent of the reduction of the damages from climate change. The table shows little or no evidence of meaningful differences¹⁴ in such

¹⁴ We have not implemented a statistical test –the most appropriate one would be the Tukey-Kramer, which allows for multiple comparisons of subsamples arising from a general sample. We feel comfortable stating that there are no significant differences in percentages across samples because i) the sample sizes are very

shares across the four split samples—a first hint that our respondents did not prove to be sensitive to one of the ways in which we conveyed the breadth of the program. This is important information, and relevant for shaping our econometric analyses, because it shows two important features of our dataset: i) that the pattern observed in the entire sample –i.e. that respondents are not too responsive to our bids— does not change across split samples; and ii) that patterns are very similar in all four samples. Both insights suggest that the unresponsiveness to bids holds in the entire sample (even when ‘dissecting’ the sample into in subsamples) and indicate that allocation to each subsample was correctly done in terms of randomness – significant differences in percentages may suggest that allocation was not complete random.

Figure 4.2 Share of votes in favour of the program according to whether the respondent believes that the survey will have an impact on policy “consequential =1” or not “consequential= 0”.

similar across subsamples; and ii) the point estimates are within one percentage point to each other. That is, standard errors are very similar as well across subsamples, and the value of the t-statistic will be very similar for all four percentages.

Figure 4.3 Distribution of total “in favour” votes within each respondent. On the X-axis, labels 0 to 7 denotes the number of times the program alternative was chosen over the no program alternative (i.e., over the status quo). The Y-axis reports the percentage of respondents that chose the program alternative zero times, one time and so on, up to those who chose the program alternative all the seven times a choice card was shown to them. This counting is “within each respondent” in the sense that it refers to numbers of times each respondent chose a program –and not to the number of times that a program was chosen.

Figure 4.2 plots the percentages in favour of the program by the cost amount separately for the respondents we dub “consequential” because they held at least some trust that their opinions would be heard by the decision-makers (55.26 of the sample) and for the remainder of the sample. Those who believed that their opinions would be heard were more likely to vote in favour of the program at any given cost level.

Figure 4.3 displays the shares of respondents who exhibited increasing number of votes in favour of the program. In other words, on the x-axis there are the number of times a respondent chose the program over the status quo out of the seven times the choice cards were shown. Some 12% were always against the program (bar “0”), shares ranging from 8% to about 14% alternated “in favour” and “against” votes, and quite surprisingly, 23% declared themselves in favour of the program seven times in the survey (bar “7”).

5.0 RESULTS

5.1 Split samples and the relevance of scope

We analysed our dataset using STATA™ (The latest version used for this Deliverable has been STATA 18.5/MP). Table 5-1 reports our estimates of the WTP for adaptation programs from each of the four combinations of split samples based on geographical coverage and the extent of the reduction of the climate change damages. Perhaps the most striking result is the absence of any pattern in the WTP figures: When a “full” program is considered—one that tackles the water supply, surface waters, coastal areas, agriculture, forests and fisheries— contrary to intuition, that would have individuals to prefer more protection from climate change to less protection, the WTP is actually less with broader geographical coverage (80%) and greater adaptation effectiveness (75%) than under the least favourable conditions (60% and 50%, respectively).

Table 5-1 WTP for adaptation from the split samples.

Geographic coverage	Damage reduction	WTP (EUR)	Standard error	lower bound of 95% CI	upper bound of 95% CI
60%	50%	1317.12	91.0034	1138.75	1495.48
80%	50%	1408.16	86.2376	1239.14	1577.18
60%	75%	1170.63	82.3677	1009.19	1332.07
80%	75%	1116.90	82.1759	955.835	1277.96

The other two combinations of coverage and damage reduction do not offer a distinguishable pattern either, and Wald tests of the null hypothesis that the WTP is the same across any two pairs either fail to reject the null or marginally reject it at the 5% significance level. We conclude that, confirming the evidence from Figure 4.3, there is no evidence of sensitivity of the WTP responses to the size of the program and to its effectiveness.

We also tested the effect of using an alternative label for nature-based solutions, a test which yields a non-significance outcome. This means that our sample is not influenced by the denomination of the measures and that using terms more evocative of positive meanings such “nature -based in place of “non-infrastructure” leaves them indifferent. In other words, they seem to keep a rational stance, at least to this aspect. We explore further the matter of measure types briefly in Section 5.2.

5.2 Pooled Sample Regressions

Based on the findings in Section 5.1, we pool the responses from the four split samples and fit random effects probit models based on equations (5) and (6) to the full sample, ignoring geographical coverage and effectiveness. The estimation results are displayed in Table 5-2 (first column). The coefficient of cost is negative and statistically significant at the conventional levels¹⁵ and the coefficients of the sector dummies

¹⁵ Significance of the coefficient of an explanatory variable is measured in terms of the p-value. If a p-value is less than 0.001, it is flagged with three stars (***). P-values equal to or less than 0.001, but above 0.01 come with 2 stars (**). One star (*) marks a p-value equal to or 0.01 and above 0.05. Higher p-values are deemed not significant.

are likewise significant and, as expected, positive. Our respondents, however, appear to react only to infrastructural measures (positively, at 2-star significance), and not to institutional or nature-based measures.

In the rest of this Section we label as “Unconstrained” the estimation in which no constraint has been imposed on the coefficient of the damage reduction and geographic coverage variables - as opposed to “constrained”, whereby such restrictions are imposed (the reasons to do that are explained in Section 5.4); “Consequential” refers to the fact that the model is applied only to the subsample of those who declared to expect policymakers to be likely to take the results of the survey into consideration for their adaptation policies; “No-straightliners” is the subsample of those respondents who voted against the program in at least one instance.

Figure 5.1 Unconstrained WTP (EUR/year) estimates, full sample. “Overall” refers to the sum of all sectors’ WTPs.

When the coefficients are translated into WTP, as shown in Figure 5.1, there appears to be a clear ranking of the covered sectors, with respondents placing the highest value on the water supply, followed by surface waters, forests, agriculture, coastal areas, and fisheries. The ranking is unaffected, and the values are similar, when the sample is limited to “consequential” respondents (fifth column in Table 5-2 and Figure 5.2).

Figure 5.2 Consequential sample only. Unconstrained WTP (EUR/year) estimates.

The only difference appears to be the higher WTP for fisheries (compared to the WTP found for the full sample). When we exclude from the estimation sample those people who voted in favour of the hypothetical program seven times (the “straightliners”, we obtain results similar to their counterparts with the full sample (last but one column in Table 5-2 and Figure 5.3).

Figure 5.3 No straightliners. Unconstrained WTP estimates.

For benefit transfer and internal validity purposes, it is important to inspect the estimation results when respondent income and education are entered in our random effects probit regressions. The second column in Table 5-2 shows similar coefficients on most variables and positive and significant coefficients on household income and a university degree dummy. When we compute the income elasticity of the WTP at

the sample's average household income, we obtain a modest 0.08. Holders of a university degree are willing to pay EUR 160 more per year for any adaptation program than persons without such an educational attainment.

Table 5-2. Probit regressions

Variables	Entire Sample				Consequential Sample		No Straightliners	
	Unconstrained, income & education		Constrained, income & education		Unconstrained	Constrained	Unconstrained	Constrained
	Unconstrained	Constrained	Unconstrained	Constrained	Unconstrained	Constrained	Unconstrained	Constrained
	Coef.	Coef.	Coef.	Coef.	Coef.	Coef.	Coef.	Coef.
Water Supply	0.3549 ***	0.3548 ***	0.1628 ***	0.1626 ***	0.2908 ***	0.1327 ***	0.3546 ***	0.1541 ***
Water Supply*Damage Reduction			0.2441 ***	0.2439 ***		0.1990 ***		0.2312 ***
Surface Water	0.2260 ***	0.2259 ***	0.0909 ***	0.0908 ***	0.2033 ***	0.0769 ***	0.2281 ***	0.0817 ***
Surface Water*Damage Reduction			0.1363 ***	0.1362 ***		0.1153 ***		0.1226 ***
Coastal Areas	0.1009 ***	0.1010 ***	0.0273 ***	0.0272 ***	0.0812 ***	0.0154	0.1072 ***	0.0177 *
Coastal Areas*Damage Reduction			0.0409 ***	0.0408 ***		0.0232		0.0265 *
Agriculture	0.2334 ***	0.2331 ***	0.1014 ***	0.1012 ***	0.1915 ***	0.0837 ***	0.2243 ***	0.0903 ***
Agriculture*Damage Reduction			0.1521 ***	0.1519 ***		0.1256 ***		0.1354 ***
Forests	0.2514 ***	0.2514 ***	0.0978 ***	0.0977 ***	0.2075 ***	0.0713 ***	0.2499 ***	0.0832 ***
Forests*Damage Reduction			0.1467 ***	0.1465 ***		0.1070 ***		0.1248 ***
Fisheries	0.0447 **	0.0446 **	0.0040	0.0038	0.0613 **	0.0160	0.0414 *	-0.0069
Fisheries*Damage Reduction			0.0060	0.0057		0.0239		-0.0103
Institutional Measures	-0.0120	-0.0120	-0.0273 ***	-0.0275 ***	0.0113	-0.0162	0.0701 **	-0.0358 ***
Institutional Measure*Damage Reduction			-0.0410 ***	-0.0413 ***		-0.0243		-0.0537 ***
Infrastructure Measures	0.0574 **	0.0573 **	-0.0079	-0.0082	0.0554 *	-0.0144	0.0017	-0.0248
Infrastructure Measure*Damage Reduction			-0.0119	-0.0123		-0.0216		-0.0373
Nature-Based Measures	-0.0212	-0.0211	-0.0363 ***	-0.0366 ***	-0.0136	-0.0416 ***	-0.0024	-0.0437 ***
Nature-Based Measure*Damage Reduction			-0.0545 ***	-0.0549 ***		-0.0624 ***		-0.0655 ***
Italy	0.4335 ***	0.3164 ***	0.6666 ***	0.5530 ***	0.6514 ***	0.8887 ***	-0.1913 ***	0.1434 ***
Spain	0.5027 ***	0.3550 ***	0.7414 ***	0.5969 ***	0.8013 ***	1.0426 ***	-0.1778 ***	0.1636 ***
Greece	0.3520 ***	0.2339 ***	0.5803 ***	0.4640 ***	0.5827 ***	0.8212 ***	-0.1921 ***	0.1369 ***
United Kingdom	0.2337 ***	0.0450 ***	0.4662 ***	0.2809 ***	0.4342 ***	0.6756 ***	-0.2210 ***	0.1128 **
Norway	0.4330 ***	0.2177 ***	0.6695 ***	0.4587 ***	0.7792 ***	1.0191 ***	-0.2171 ***	0.1178 **
Finland	-0.0199	-0.1664	0.2177 ***	0.0751	0.3486	0.5872 ***	-0.4232 ***	-0.0853 *
Income		0.0356 ***		0.0345 ***				
College Degree		0.1507 ***		0.1529 ***				
Program Cost	-0.0009421 ***	-0.0009 ***	-0.0009367 ***	-0.000937 ***	-0.000783 ***	-0.000779 ***	-0.000950 ***	-0.000944 ***
Rho	0.6551	0.6551	0.6550	0.6533	0.5910	0.5911	0.3873	0.3880
Sample	62,020	62,020	62,020	62,020	34,419	34,419	47,719	47,719
Groups	8,860	8,860	8,860	8,860	4,917	4917	6,817	6,817

5.3 Country-specific Regressions

Based on common knowledge on the main features of the countries in our sample, we expected the public in countries in Northern Europe to be more concerned about forests and fisheries, and less concerned about sea level rise or drought, than people in Southern Europe, and the respective WTP figures to mirror such concerns. We fit a separate random effects probit model to the responses from each country and used the estimated coefficients to compute the mean/median WTP to cover each sector as well as the WTP for a “full” program that covers all six sectors.

The results from this exercise are reported in Table 5-3. There is clear evidence of heterogeneity in the value of each resource or sector across the countries, and it is a bit surprising that Italian and UK respondents appear to care about fisheries much more than other countries (e.g., Norway, Spain) that have historically relied extensively on fishing. Italy and the UK appear to be the countries that place the highest value on protecting their coastlines, while the Italian respondents are the ones with the lowest degree of concern about agriculture. At EUR 600, the value of the water supply is highest among the Spanish respondents, although the water supply is the most highly valued resources in all countries.

We also looked into the feasibility of using country-level regressions as starting points for benefit transfer. Our benefit transfer exercise is described in detail in deliverable D6.2. Here we note that a key precondition for that procedure to work is that the variables that drive the benefit transfer must be significant. The variable used in our benefit transfer exercise of D6.2 are household income and education. It turns out that performing such exercise is only viable using the pooled sample model of Table 5-2, second column. Using country-level regression to this purpose is not feasible, because income becomes insignificant everywhere but in Norway and education becomes insignificant everywhere but in Norway and Italy.

Table 5-3 Separate model for each country: WTP for each sector and overall predicted by random effects probit.

WTP (EUR/year) for:	Finland	Greece	Italy	Norway	Spain	UK
Water Supply	406.51	337.70	319.00	396.05	605.46	280.38
Surface Waters	252.47	230.74	298.06	208.02	290.16	212.46
Coastal Areas	58.06	86.27	200.41	82.87	85.46	140.30
Agriculture	227.71	297.29	196.77	303.54	370.00	190.64
Forests	274.67	296.45	238.18	210.68	317.90	165.22
Fisheries	-8.93	-16.33	59.97	2.24	5.39	81.52
Full program	1210.48	1232.13	1312.39	1203.39	1674.36	1070.52

5.4 . Program Effectiveness: Constrained Regressions

In Section 5.1 we noted that there is no evidence that the WTP responses were sensitive to the programs’ geographical coverage and the reduction of climate change damages. If one interprets the latter as the effectiveness of adaptation policies, respondents do not seem to be attentive to it.

What happens if we *impose* that respondent had been more aware of these features of the programs, creating restrictions on the parameters of the random effects probit that force the WTP for programs that reduce climate change damages by 75% to be 75/50=1.5 times that for programs that reduce climate change damages only by 50%?

We report the results of this exercise in the columns marked as “Constrained” in Table 5-2 (the third, seventh and last columns) and Figure 5.4, Figure 5.5, Figure 5.6. The ranking of the various sectors and natural resources described in Section 5.2 is maintained. Intuition would suggest that a weighted average of the WTP figures for the less and the more effective variants of the program should be equal to the WTP amounts displayed in Figure 5.1 (those from the unrestricted model), but, as shown in Figure 5.4 this is clearly not the case for coastal areas and fisheries, whose WTP values are now lower. Specifically, the WTP for coastal areas is EUR 29 in the less protective and EUR 73 in the more protective variants of the program. These values are less than the WTP for coastal areas from the unrestricted model (EUR 107). Likewise, the WTP figures for fisheries and aquaculture are EUR 4 and EUR 11, respectively—a sharp decline with respect to that of the unrestricted model (about EUR 47).

Figure 5.4. Constrained WTP estimates. Entire sample.

Figure 5.5. Constrained WTP estimates. Consequential sample.

Figure 5.6. Constrained WTP estimates. No straightliners.

The WTP figures from the “consequential” respondents (Figure 5.5) are more in line with our expectations based on the unrestricted estimates for fisheries and aquaculture but exhibit the same decline as for the full sample for coastal areas. When the sample excludes respondents who declared themselves in favour of the program seven times during the survey (Figure 5.6), we even obtain negative and insignificant WTP values for fisheries and aquaculture protection.

6.0 CONCLUSIONS

The research presented in this deliverable is a first attempt to understand the degree of acceptance of adaptation solutions by the public in Europe and to quantify it in terms of willingness-to-pay (WTP) for adaptation policy measures, by eliciting the preferences of the public for adaptation solutions using a DCE approach and estimating econometrically the related WTPs. DCE studies in the literature on adaptation generally evaluate one or few specific adaptation measures to be deployed at a specific location, focusing, in most instances, on agricultural and coastal adaptation. To our knowledge, there are no studies taking a broader stance and evaluating the WTP of the residents in one or more countries towards adaptation in general, or in the various sectors for which adaptation measures may be needed. Our study, that covers six European countries, and six adaptation sectors, is a first attempt to arrive to such general WTP estimates for adaptation Europe.

To this purpose, we designed a survey to be conducted among 9072 respondents in six European countries (roughly 1500 per country). Respondents were engaged in a Discrete Choice Experiment in a referendum format, whereby alternative policy packages were compared to the status quo (i.e. no new adaptation program).

Our econometric analysis of the dataset thus collected yielded interesting and to some extent, surprising results. Key parameters were significant and with the sign we expected. In particular the coefficient on cost, negative and statistically significant, allows to compute overall WTP; similarly, sector-specific WTPs could also be easily estimated. Differentiating WTP across types of measures is however not recommended with our dataset, as only the presence of infrastructure triggers a significant reaction. Also, consistently using a label evocative of positive values instead of a technically equivalent but value-neutral one, when referring to a class of measures to be evaluated- that is, always using the label “nature-based” instead of “ non-infrastructure” - did not trigger a significantly higher WTPs from our respondents.

Our most comprehensive WTP estimate, for policy packages covering all resources and sectors considered in the DCE, is quite high (EUR 1346 a year). In terms of sector-specific WTPs, there appears to be a clear ranking of WTP across sectors: water supply ranks first, followed by surface waters, forests, agriculture, coastal areas, and fisheries. Restricting the sample to those who expect their answers to be taken into consideration by policymakers (the “consequential” respondents) does not affect the ranking, and hardly affects WTP values. Results are also robust to excluding those respondents who voted in favour of the hypothetical program all seven times.

Income elasticity of the WTP computed at the sample’s average household income turns out to be very small (0.08) but significant. Conversely, having completed a university education results in respondents willing to pay EUR 160 more for any adaptation program than persons with lower educational attainments.

There is clear evidence of heterogeneity in the value of each resource or sector across the countries. Italy and the UK are the countries placing the highest value on protecting their coastlines, while the Italian

respondents are the ones with the lowest degree of concern about agriculture. Adaptation policy targeting water supply, the most highly valued resource in all countries, reaches its top WTP in Spain.

Imposing constraints on the coefficient of the damage reduction and geographic coverage variables to mimic the behaviour of respondents that are mindful of the possible different levels of geographic coverage and damage reduction (that is, constraining these parameters to vary proportionally to the prospected changes in coverage and reduction) does not affect the ranking of the various sectors and natural resources. Intuition would suggest that a weighted average of the WTP figures for the less and the more effective variants of the program should be equal to the WTP from the unrestricted model, but this is clearly not the case for coastal areas and fisheries, whose WTP values are lower in the constrained model. Restricting the analysis to respondents believing that policymakers will take their responses into due account, yields WTP values more in line with our expectations based on the unrestricted estimates for fisheries and aquaculture but exhibits the same decline as for the full sample for coastal areas.

There are valuable takeaways for our project and for EU adaptation policy in these results. From TransformAr's perspective (in particular, in view of the goals of Work Package 6), our WTP results provides the empirical basis for a comprehensive assessment of the acceptance of adaptation actions in Europe. We found a specification of our econometric estimations that can be used to perform a Benefit Transfer exercise to all other European countries to estimate the WTPs for adaptation across Europe¹⁶. We report about this exercise is in Deliverable D.6.2.

In an acceptability perspective, we can conclude that our demonstrators' adaptation solutions stand good chances to be warmly welcomed in the areas where they are being deployed, but those dealing with water resources are likely to meet the highest interest, and those dealing with fisheries to trigger less support within the public.

We had hoped to document sensitivity to scope of the policy programs proposed to respondents in our DCE, but our findings did not support that. The practical implication is that WTP estimates arising from this study are not as useful for benefit transfer as we wished. However, there is evidence that failure to pass scope test may in part be due to the use of utility functions that follow neoclassical utility theory in the sense that are directionally bounded (Amiran et al., 2010). That is, there is a trade-off in terms of passing sensitivity scope when using theoretically consistent utility functions versus using more flexible functions. In terms of the validity of our study, these previous findings suggest that a failure to satisfy scope tests should not be used as a basis for irrevocably rejecting contingent valuation studies (Amiran and Hagen, 2010).

Moreover, this lack of scope sensitivity, although not our most preferred outcome, is in any case, informative: it can be interpreted as a strong, underlying sense of urgency with which European residents look at future climate threats: what matters the most to them is that policymakers start taking effective actions against these threats.

Also, we did expect different sensitivities to different sectors and resources according to the specific situation of each country, but the lower and upper end of the spectrum of our WTPs are somewhat surprising (very high for water resources in Spain, very low for fisheries everywhere). Future research on

¹⁶ That this, the one including income and education among the explanatory variables (the second probit model in Table 5-2).

this dataset can further explore acceptance by looking more into the details of specific characteristics of the households in this sample: is WTP for coastal adaptation or fisheries going to be higher among coastal residents? Or the WTP for agricultural adaptation is going to be higher in rural areas?

Despite these limitations, we have built a robust approach for evaluating the WTP of European residents for climate adaptation action, which sheds light on the economic value of the climate damages to the sector and resources we considered, to a level of generality never attempted before. Our results can inform other activities of the project (beside the benefit-transfer exercise of Task 6.2, these results can provide relevant food for thought during networking and stakeholder engagement activities of the project), and we hope that they will ultimately provide useful insight to the scientific community and to policymakers in Europe and beyond.

REFERENCES

- Alberini, A., Bigano, A. Ščasný, M., Zvěřinová, I., (2018). Preferences for Energy Efficiency vs. Renewables: What Is the Willingness to Pay to Reduce CO₂ Emissions? *Ecological Economics*, V. 144, 171-185, ISSN 0921-8009.
- Alcon F., Tapsuwan S., Brouwer R., de Miguel M.D., (2014) Adoption of irrigation water policies to guarantee water supply: A choice experiment, *Environmental Science & Policy*, Volume 44, Pages 226-236, ISSN 1462-9011, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2014.08.012>.
- Amiran, E. Y. and Hagen, D. A. (2010). The scope trials: Variation in sensitivity to scope and WTP with directionally bounded utility functions. *Journal of Environmental Economics and Management*, 59(3), 293-301.
- Arora A., Bansal S., Ward P.S., (2019). Do farmers value rice varieties tolerant to droughts and floods? Evidence from a discrete choice experiment in Odisha, India, *Water Resources and Economics*, Volume 25, Pages 27-41, ISSN 2212-4284, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wre.2018.03.001>.
- Bro A.S, Ortega D.L., Clay D.C. and Richardson R.B. (2020) Understanding individuals' incentives for climate change adaptation in Nicaragua's coffee sector, *Climate and Development*, 12:4, 332-342, DOI: [10.1080/17565529.2019.1619506](https://doi.org/10.1080/17565529.2019.1619506)
- Buckell, J., Buchanan, J., Wordsworth, S., Becker, F., Morrell, L., Roope, L., Kaur, A., Abel, L. (2020). Hypothetical Bias. In: *Catalogue of Bias*. <https://catalogofbias.org/>
- Carson R.T., Louviere J.J, Wei E. (2010). Alternative Australian climate change plans: The public's views, *Energy Policy*, Volume 38, Issue 2, Pages 902-911, ISSN 0301-4215, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2009.10.041>.
- Carson R.T., Groves T., List J.A. (2014). Consequentiality: a theoretical and experimental exploration of a single binary choice. *J Assoc Environ Resour Econ* 1(1/2):171–207. <https://doi.org/10.1086/676450>
- Caussade S., Ortúzar J de D., Rizzi L.I., Hensher D.A. (2005). Assessing the influence of design dimensions on stated choice experiment estimates. *Transportation Research Part B: Methodological*, 39:621–640. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trb.2004.07.006>
- Chen, Z., S. K. Swallow, and. Yue I. T. (2020). Non-participation and Heterogeneity in Stated Preferences: A Double Hurdle Latent Class Approach for Climate Change Adaptation Plans and Ecosystem Services. *Environmental and Resource Economics*77: 35–67
- Colombo, S., Budziński, W., Czajkowski, M., & Glenk, K. (2022). The relative performance of ex-ante and ex-post measures to mitigate hypothetical and strategic bias in a stated preference study. *Journal of Agricultural Economics*, 73(3), 845-873.
- Dachary-Bernard, J., H. Rey-Valette, and Rulleau E. B. (2019). Preferences Among Coastal and Inland Residents Relating to Managed Retreat: Influence of Risk Perception in Acceptability of Relocation Strategies. *Journal of Environmental Management* 232: 772–780.

de Bekker-Grob E.W., Donkers B., Jonker M.F., Stolk E.A. (2015) Sample size requirements for discrete choice experiments in healthcare: a practical guide. *Patient* 8:373–384. DOI: 10.1007/s40271-015-0118-z

Doherty E., Mellett S., Norton D., McDermott T.K.J., O’ Hora D., Ryan M. (2021). A discrete choice experiment exploring farmer preferences for insurance against extreme weather events, *Journal of Environmental Management*, Volume 290, 112607, ISSN 0301-4797, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2021.112607>.

Doyon M., Saulais L., Ruffieux B., and Bweli D. (2015). Hypothetical bias for private goods: does cheap talk make a difference? *Theoretical Economics Letters*, 5(6):749{756, 2015. 23)

Dugstad, A., Grimsrud, K. M., Kipperberg, G., Lindhjem, H., & Navrud, S. (2021). Scope elasticity of willingness to pay in discrete choice experiments. *Environmental and Resource Economics*, 80(1), 21-57.

Furuya, J., Omori, K. and Aizaki, H. (2021). Toward the development of a weather index insurance for rice farmers in the coastal region of Myanmar. *Paddy Water Environ* **19**, 255–260. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10333-021-00862-7>

Haab, T., Lewis, L. Y., & Whitehead, J. (2020). State of the art of contingent valuation. *Oxford research encyclopedia of environmental science*. DOI:10.1093/acrefore/9780199389414.013.450

Johnston R.J., Boyle K.J., Adamowicz W., Bennett J., Brouwer R., Cameron T.A., Hanemann W.M. et al. (2017) Contemporary guidance for stated preference studies. *J Assoc. Environ. Resour. Econ.* 4(2):319–405. <https://doi.org/10.1086/691697>

Jørgensen S.L, Termansen M., Unai Pascual U. (2020). Natural insurance as condition for market insurance: Climate change adaptation in agriculture, *Ecological Economics*, Volume 169, 106489, ISSN 0921-8009, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolecon.2019.106489>.

Khanal U., Wilson C., Lee B. and Hoang V.-N. (2018). Smallholder farmers’ participation in climate change adaptation programmes: understanding preferences in Nepal, *Climate Policy*, 18:7, 916-927, DOI: [10.1080/14693062.2017.1389688](https://doi.org/10.1080/14693062.2017.1389688)

Lancsar, E. and Louviere, J. (2008). *Distinguishing between Conjoint Analysis and Discrete Choice Experiments with Implications for Stated Preference and Welfare Elicitation*, Sydney: University of Technology, Sydney.

Liski, A. H., M. J. Koetse, and M. J. Metzger (2019). Addressing Awareness Gaps in Environmental Valuation: Choice Experiments with Citizens in the Inner Forth, Scotland. *Regional Environmental Change* 19: 2217–2229. DOI:10.1007/s10113-018-01458-4.

Maiella, R., La Malva, P., Marchetti, D., Pomarico, E., Di Crosta, A., Palumbo, R., Cetara, L., Di Domenico, A., & Verrocchio, M. C. (2020). The psychological distance and climate change: A systematic review on the mitigation and adaptation behaviors. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 11, Article 568899. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2020.568899>

Mariel, P., Hoyos, D., Meyerhoff, J., Czajkowski, M., Dekker, T., Glenk, K. and Thiene, M. (2021). Developing the Questionnaire. Chapter 2 in: *Environmental Valuation with Discrete Choice*

- Experiments: Guidance on Design, Implementation and Data Analysis, 7-36. Springer Nature Switzerland, Cham, Switzerland. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-62669-3>
- McFadden, D. (1974). Conditional Logit Analysis of Qualitative Choice Behavior. In P. Zarembka (ed.), *Frontiers in Econometrics*. New York: Academic Press, 105-142.
- Nthambi M., Markova-Nenova N., Wätzold F. (2021). Quantifying Loss of Benefits from Poor Governance of Climate Change Adaptation Projects: A Discrete Choice Experiment with Farmers in Kenya. *Ecological Economics*, Volume 179, 106831, ISSN 0921-8009, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolecon.2020.106831>.
- OECD/Eurostat/UNESCO Institute for Statistics (2015). *ISCED 2011 Operational Manual: Guidelines for Classifying National Education Programmes and Related Qualifications*, OECD Publishing, Paris, <https://doi.org/10.1787/9789264228368-en>.
- Oliveira, S., Pinto, L.M.C. (2021). Choice experiments to elicit the users' preferences for coastal erosion management: the case of *Praia da Amorosa*. *Environ Dev Sustain* **23**, 9749–9765. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10668-020-00768-0>
- Oijstaeijen, W. V.; Passel, S. V.; Back, P.; Cools, J. (2022). The Politics of Green Infrastructure: A Discrete Choice Experiment with Flemish Local Decision-Makers. *Ecological Economics*, *199*, 107493. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolecon.2022.107493>.
- Pröbstl-Haider, U., Mostegl, N.M., Kelemen-Finan, J. *et al.* (2016). Farmers' Preferences for Future Agricultural Land Use Under the Consideration of Climate Change. *Environmental Management* **58**, 446–464. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00267-016-0720-4>
- Remoundou, K., P. Diaz-Simal, P. Koundouri, and B. Rulleau, (2015). Valuing Climate Change Mitigation: A Choice Experiment on a Coastal and Marine Ecosystem. *Ecosystem Services* *11*: 87–94. DOI:10.1016/j.ecoser.2014.11.003.
- Schaafsma M., Ferrini S., Turner R. K., (2019). Assessing smallholder preferences for incentivised climate-smart agriculture using a discrete choice experiment, *Land Use Policy*, Volume 88, 104153, ISSN 0264-8377, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landusepol.2019.104153>.
- Ščasný, M., Zvěřinová I., Czajkowski M., Kyselá E., Zagórska K., (2017). Public acceptability of climate change mitigation policies: a discrete choice experiment *Clim. Pol.*, *17* (sup 1), pp. S111-S130, [10.1080/14693062.2016.1248888](https://doi.org/10.1080/14693062.2016.1248888)
- Train, K. E. (2009). *Discrete Choice Methods with Simulation*. Second edition. Cambridge, United Kingdom: Cambridge University Press.
- Tykcinski, O. E., Pittman, T. S., & Tuttle, E. S. (1995). Inaction inertia: Foregoing future benefits as a result of an initial failure to act. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, *68*, 793–803.
- Waldman K.B. and Richardson R.B. (2018). Confronting Tradeoffs Between Agricultural Ecosystem Services and Adaptation to Climate Change in Mali, *Ecological Economics*, Volume 150, Pages 184-193, ISSN 0921-8009, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolecon.2018.04.003>.

Welling, M., Zawojka, E. & Sagebiel, J. (2022). Information, Consequentiality and Credibility in Stated Preference Surveys: A Choice Experiment on Climate Adaptation. *Environ Resource Econ* **82**, 257–283. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10640-022-00675-0>

Wirth H., Klaus Pforr K., The European Union Statistics on Income and Living Conditions after 15 Years, *European Sociological Review*, Volume 38, Issue 5, October 2022, Pages 832–848, <https://doi.org/10.1093/esr/jcac024>

World Health Organization (2012). How to Conduct a Discrete Choice Experiment for Health Workforce Recruitment and Retention in Remote and Rural Areas: A user guide with case studies. ISBN 978 92 4 150480 5. https://www.who.int/hrh/resources/DCE_UserGuide_WEB.pdf?ua=1

Wunsch, A., Meyerhoff, J. and Rehdanz, K., (2022). A test–retest analysis of stated preferences in uncertain times, *Economic Analysis and Policy*, Elsevier, vol. 73(C), pages 725-736. DOI: 10.1016/j.eap.2021.12.021

ANNEX 1: THE QUESTIONNAIRE

The following is the final version of the questionnaire, as revised by the authors and Dynata on October 3rd, 2023, and used for administering the full-sample online survey in the field. It replaces the version of May 23rd, 2023, which was the most up-to-date version when this report was first submitted.

Please note that this is the version using “Nature-based” within the split sample treatment “Nature-based vs. Non-Infrastructure”. This version will be administered to half of our sample, that is 750 respondents in each country, 4500 in total. The remaining 4500 respondent saw “Non-Infrastructure” in all instances in which “Nature-based” appears in the text below. For the convenience of the reader, these instances are marked with an asterisk.

Survey on the acceptability of climate change adaptation options

To be conducted in Six EU countries

Consent

Welcome to this survey! This survey is about measures and initiatives to limit the adverse consequences of climate change in Europe.

This survey is being conducted in six European countries by a consortium of universities and research organizations led by the University of Antwerp, Belgium. This study is part of the Project TransformAr, which is funded by the European Commission.

Your participation and your opinions are very important to us. This survey is not a quiz. There are no right or wrong answers to our questions. We are simply interested in your honest opinions.

This form contains important information about the reasons for undertaking this study, what you will be asked to do if you decide to be in the study, and the way information about you will be used if you choose to participate.

Informed consent

By this informed consent **you confirm that:**

- you are 18 years or older and
- you are competent to provide this consent;
- you have read the information about the survey ([click here to read the information sheet](#));
- you are voluntarily taking part in this survey.

Time Required: We estimate that it will take you approximately **25 minutes** to answer the questions in this survey. If you do not **complete the questionnaire within a week** it will be assumed that you have withdrawn your consent, and none of your responses will be retained.

By completing the questionnaire, you **agree** that anonymous data from the questionnaire may be provided to third parties for non-commercial research. Any change to the above conditions is possible only with your explicit approval.

This project has received funding from European Union's Horizon H2020 innovation action programme under grant agreement 101036683.

[1] I would like to participate in the survey and give my consent

[2] I prefer not to participate

INFORMATION ON THE SURVEY (INFORMATION SHEET)

About the project

This survey is being carried out by Dynata (you can find [here](#) more information about Dynata's privacy policy) on behalf of the University of Antwerp and the Euro-Mediterranean Center on Climate Change (CMCC) as part of the project "*TransformAr - Transformational adaptation to reduce climate-related risks*", funded by the EU Commission within the Horizon 2020 Programme under grant agreement 101036683.

You can find more information about the Project and its Partners [here](#).

Purpose of this survey

This survey is about measures and initiatives to limit the adverse consequences of climate change in Europe. The TransformAr project studies the development of concrete climate change adaptation solutions in Europe, and this survey aims to gauge the attitudes and opinions of the people in order to better inform the project's research and the policymakers with whom the project's results will be shared.

Confidentiality and sharing of the results

The data that you will share will be handled as confidentially as possible adhering to all pertinent standards and legislation. To minimize the risks of breaching confidentiality, we will collect only data that we need for the purposes of the described research project.

This survey will not require the insertion of personal data or information that may identify the relevant users, which will remain anonymous also to the researchers involved in the Project. However, before the publication or presentation of the results of this study, we will make sure that eventual personal data and other personally identifiable information (if any) will not be used. Hence, we will make sure that no answers you give can be traced back to you. Nonetheless, all partner institutions involved in the TransformAr project adhere to the provision set in the European Union's General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR).

All scientific reports or publications based on this survey will present summary statistical information, such as averages or ranges. No information will ever be disclosed that could be linked to a particular person.

Who is responsible for the data collected in this study?

The work in the survey is being led by Andrea Bigano, PhD on behalf of the TransformAr's Partners. If you have any questions about this survey, you may contact Dr. Bigano at andrea.bigano@cmcc.it.

What are the benefits of participating in this study?

Panelists will be compensated according to the usual point scheme of the Dynata program. The study itself can be used to help design policies that better address people's concerns about climate change.

What if I have any ethical concerns about this research?

This survey has been reviewed and approved by TransformAr's coordination team. If you are concerned about how this research is being conducted, you can contact the leader of the research team.

For more information

If you have any further questions or concerns about this survey, please visit the TransformAr webpage at www.transformar.eu or contact Andrea Bigano (andrea.bigano@cmcc.it)

Section 0. Questions for sampling quotas

Q.1 What is your gender?

- [1] male
- [2] female
- [3] non-binary
- [4] prefer not to say

Q.1B How old are you? (QA, range 1-99, Screen out if <18)

||

Q.2 Please enter the postal code of your place of residence:

||_|_|_|

Q2.a Do you live:

- [1] in a densely populated urban area
- [2] in the suburbs or in small town
- [3] In a rural area
- [4] I don't know

Q3. Which of the following categories best describes your education level – that is, which is the highest education cycle you completed?

(NB. As this question is programmed differently for each country, see below the corresponding screen for the UK)

Which of the following categories best describes your education level – that is, which is the highest education cycle you completed?

- Primary education
Skills for Life certificates
left school after age 11 without certificate
- Lower secondary education
- Completed secondary school (GCSEs and/or A Levels); (Modern) Apprenticeship, Advanced (Modern) Apprenticeship, Vocational A-level
- Completed some university/college; Edexcel/BTEC/BEC/TEC Higher National Certificate (HNC) or equivalent
HE Access
- Nursing certificate, Teacher training, HE Diploma, Edexcel/BTEC/BEC/TEC - Higher National Diploma (HND), OCR/RSA - Higher Diploma, City and Guilds -
Foundation Degree (FdA, FdSc etc)
- University/College degree (BA, BSc., BEd., BEng. etc).
- Masters Degree, M.Phil, Post-Graduate Diplomas and Certificates
5 year University/CNAA first Degree (MB, BDS, BV etc)
- Ph.D, D.Phil or equivalent
- I prefer not to answer

BackContinue

Q4. What is your household's total net monthly income from all sources? Please think of your take-home income after tax)

Please include all sources of income such as child support and other state support, interest, and other revenues. If you don't know the exact figure, please give an estimate.

(NB. As this question is programmed differently for each country, see below the corresponding screen for the UK)

What is your household's total net monthly income from all sources? Please think of your take-home income after tax)

Please include all sources of income such as child support and other state support, interest, and other revenues. If you don't know the exact figure, please give an estimate.

- Less than 540 pounds
- Between 541 and 820 pounds
- Between 821 and 1090 pounds
- Between 1091 and 1360 pounds
- Between 1361 and 1630 pounds
- Between 1631 and 2180 pounds
- Between 2181 and 2720 pounds
- Between 2721 and 3260 pounds
- Between 3261 and 3810 pounds
- Between 3811 and 4350 pounds
- Between 4351 and 4900 pounds
- Between 4901 and 5440 pounds
- Between 5441 and 5980 pounds
- Between 5981 and 6530 pounds
- Between 6531 and 8160 pounds
- Between 8161 and 13600 pounds
- Over 13600 pounds
- I don't know
- I prefer not to answer

Back Continue

Section A. Climate change knowledge and concern.

The scientific community and governments alike agree that the climate is rapidly changing and will continue to do so over the next decades.

By climate, we mean the average weather (including temperature and precipitation patterns) in a place over many years.

Climate change is caused by the use of oil, gas and coal to generate electricity, heat buildings, for factories, and in transport. When these fossil fuels burn, they release greenhouse gases—mostly carbon dioxide (CO₂). Greenhouse gases are also released during agricultural activities, by livestock, and while drilling gas and oil. These gases trap the sun's heat and cause the planet's temperature to rise. The Earth is now about 1.2° C warmer than it was in 1850—and the concentration of CO₂ in the atmosphere has risen by 50% since.

The most important consequences of climate change include:

- sea level rise,

- damage to crops and vegetation,
 - more frequent and intense heat waves,
 - changing precipitation patterns that may cause severe floods in some places and extreme droughts in others,
 - extreme weather events (massive storms, heat waves, etc.),
 - wildfires, and
 - loss of plant and animal species.
- These impacts may force people to move to other locations.

What can be done to slow down or stop climate change? This can be accomplished by reducing greenhouse gas emissions, switching to renewable energy sources, planting trees, preserving forests to capture CO₂, changing agricultural practices and extracting less gas and oil.

The effects of climate change are already being experienced in many places, in terms of rising sea levels, coastal erosion, floods or droughts, forest fires, heat waves, and other extreme weather events. They affect virtually every aspect of everyday life and every sector of the economy. For example, rising sea levels erode the structures that support bridges and buildings in coastal areas. They also compromise the quality of groundwater and/or water wells in coastal areas. Excessive heat causes damage to railroad tracks and other transportation infrastructure. It can also threaten the electricity grid just at the time when it is needed most (during heat waves when people and businesses need air conditioning), and even the generation of electricity. Changing precipitations and droughts damage crops and forests and can compromise the water supply.

Q.5. Before this survey, had you heard about the following possible consequences of climate change?

Climate change consequences	YES	NO
Rising sea levels	[]	[]
Damage to crops and vegetation	[]	[]
More frequent and intense heat waves	[]	[]
Floods	[]	[]
Droughts	[]	[]
Other extreme weather events	[]	[]
Loss of plants and animal species	[]	[]
Some harmful, invasive species will spread to new areas	[]	[]
Mass migrations	[]	[]

Q.6 How concerned are you personally about the following consequences of climate change? Please rate your level of concern about each of these consequences on a scale from 1 to 5, where 1=not at all and 5=very highly.

Climate change consequences	1 Not at all	2	3	4	5 Very highly	Don't know
Rising sea levels	1	2	3	4	5	6
Damage to crops and vegetation	1	2	3	4	5	6
More frequent and intense heat waves	1	2	3	4	5	6
Floods	1	2	3	4	5	6
Droughts	1	2	3	4	5	6
Other extreme weather events	1	2	3	4	5	6
Loss of plants and animal species	1	2	3	4	5	6
Some harmful, invasive species will spread to new areas	1	2	3	4	5	6
Mass migrations	1	2	3	4	5	6

Q7. Based on your knowledge and experience, how would you rate climate change risks in your country? Please rate each of the following items on a scale from 1 to 5, where 1 = low or no risk, and 5 = very high risk.

	Climate Risk					
	1= low or no risk	2	3	4	5=very high risk	6= don't know
Water supplies for irrigation	1	2	3	4	5	6
Structures, buildings and people in coastal areas	1	2	3	4	5	6
The agricultural sector	1	2	3	4	5	6
The quality of water in rivers, lakes, and lagoons	1	2	3	4	5	6

Forest health	1	2	3	4	5	6
The water supply in cities and rural areas	1	2	3	4	5	6
Marine ecosystems	1	2	3	4	5	6
Urban areas	1	2	3	4	5	6
The manufacturing sector	1	2	3	4	5	6
The population during heat waves	1	2	3	4	5	6
Rural areas	1	2	3	4	5	6
The service sector	1	2	3	4	5	6

Section B. Adaptation.

To limit the adverse consequences of climate change, we can put in place policies, measures, and individual actions. In this questionnaire, we will focus on these policies, measures and actions, and will refer to them using the term “adaptation.”

The purpose of adaptation measures is to reduce climate change damages to people, buildings and structures, and economic activity in general.

Adaptation measures can be taken by individuals or by the government. An example of individual adaptation is when people run the air conditioning when it is too hot.

Public adaptation programs may be undertaken by local or national governments, are generally paid with tax revenues, and bring benefits to the community. They include, for example,

- beach nourishment to combat beach erosion and sea level rise¹⁷,
- regulations to prevent building homes in areas subject to floods,
- protecting the population from extreme weather events, and
- securing water sources in the event of droughts.

Public adaptation programs can rely on

- **Infrastructure measures** (building or strengthening structures)
- **nature-based* approaches** such as
 - using plants to limit soil erosion and runoff¹⁸,
 - restoring wetlands to limit floods and help protect water quality in rivers, streams, and lakes,
 - switch to climate-resistant crops or forest management practices to improve resilience to harsh climate conditions
- **institutional measures**, such as regulations, alerts to the population in advance of extreme weather events, and preparations to make sure that vital services (for example, water or electricity) are available during extreme weather events or other disruptions.

Q.8. Based on your knowledge and experience, how would you rate the adaptation potential in your country? Please rate each of the following items on a scale from 1 to 5, where 1=lowest adaptation potential and 5=highest adaptation potential.

In judging the adaptation potential, please think of physical constraints¹⁹ and opportunities, as well as available resources. Tougher physical constraints limit the adaptation potential, whereas more resources (financial, technical and/or know-how) increase the adaptation potential.

¹⁷ Beach nourishment means bringing sand to beaches to combat beach erosion.

¹⁸ These practices have been used by farmers for decades to reduce soil erosion. These have been extensively tested in riparian areas (that is, along land alongside creeks, streams, gullies, rivers and in wetlands)

¹⁹ By “physical constraints” we mean here any physical features that may hinder putting in place adaptation measures, such as the geographical characteristics of a given area

	Adaptation Potential					
	1= lowest	2	3	4	5= highest	6= don't know
Water supplies for irrigation	1	2	3	4	5	6
Structures, buildings and people in coastal areas	1	2	3	4	5	6
The agricultural sector	1	2	3	4	5	6
The quality of water in rivers, lakes, and lagoons	1	2	3	4	5	6
Forest health	1	2	3	4	5	6
The water supply in cities and rural areas	1	2	3	4	5	6
Marine ecosystems	1	2	3	4	5	6
Urban areas	1	2	3	4	5	6
The manufacturing sector	1	2	3	4	5	6
The population during heat waves	1	2	3	4	5	6
Rural areas	1	2	3	4	5	6
The service sector	1	2	3	4	5	6

This questionnaire focuses on climate change risks and adaptation in six areas or sectors of concern:

- Water supply for drinking and all other residential, commercial, and industrial uses
- Rivers, lakes, and other water bodies
- Coastal areas
- Agriculture

- Forests
- Fisheries and aquaculture

We describe them briefly below.

	Area of concern	Climate change risks	Examples of adaptation measures
	<p>Water supply for drinking and all other residential, commercial, and industrial uses.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Droughts - Saltwater intrusion - Water scarcity 	<p><i>Infrastructure Measures</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Organize water storage (in reservoirs) - Build desalination plants <p><i>Institutional Measures</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Import water from other locations - Establish and coordinate water rights markets <p><i>Nature-based* Measures</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Restore wetlands to help recharge aquifers.
	<p>Rivers and water bodies (lakes, lagoons, etc.)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Higher water temperatures are bad for certain species - Floods and runoff during extreme weather events deposit sediments, and worsen water quality - Floods cause damage to people and property - Floods may destroy or damage bridges, and infrastructure 	<p><i>Infrastructure Measures</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Raise river banks - Reinforce infrastructure (bridges, etc.) <p><i>Institutional Measures</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Improve early warning systems for extreme events - Technical standards for new and existing infrastructure to ensure it is resilient to climate change

			<p><i>Nature-based* Measures</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Use plants and wetlands to limit runoff and help maintain water quality
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Coastal flooding - Sea level rise 	<p><i>Infrastructure Measures</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Build or install barriers / floating barriers - Restore beaches - Strengthen existing infrastructure
	<p>Coastal areas</p>		<p><i>Institutional Measures</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Technical standards for new and existing infrastructure to ensure it is resilient to climate change - Early warning systems for extreme events
			<p><i>Nature-based* Measures</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Dunes, beach nourishment, wetlands. - Coral banks and mussels have been found to mitigate sea level rise and coastal erosion.
	<p>Agriculture</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Loss of crops due to drought, changed temperature and precipitation patterns - This may affect high-value crops (e.g., certain wine grapes) 	<p><i>Infrastructure Measures</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - More efficient irrigation systems (e.g., drip irrigation instead of sprinkling) - Strengthen irrigation networks <p><i>Institutional Measures</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Plans and regulations for land use to better cope with climate change

			<p><i>Nature-based* Measures</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Climate-resistant crops - Climate-resistant breeds of livestock
			<p><i>Infrastructure Measures</i></p> <p>n.a.</p>
			<p><i>Institutional Measures</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Strengthen fire prevention systems - Monitor species of plants and insects, and prompt eradication of harmful, invasive plants and insects
			<p><i>Nature-based* Measures</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Sustainable forest management practices
			<p><i>Infrastructure Measures</i></p> <p>n.a.</p>
			<p><i>Institutional Measures</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Adjust catch quotas to changes in fish population induced by climate change - Monitoring of environment and fish health - Promote new technologies, breeding and feeding programs

Forests

Fisheries and aquaculture (fish and seafood farming)

Nature-based Measures*

- Climate-resistant breeds

NB. Clickable icons were shown at questions Q9 to Q13, through which the respondent was able to open and read again each area description, as shown below:

(If you need to refresh your memory about one or more areas of concern, please click on the corresponding icon)

Q.9 We list below a number of possible adaptation options. For each of them, please let us know whether—to the best of your knowledge—they are currently being implemented in your country and in the area where you live. Please let us know if you have never heard of them before.

Adaptation measure	Implemented in my country	Implemented in my region, province or city	Not implemented	Don't know if it is being implemented	Never heard of it
Structures (seawalls, dams) to prevent flooding of coastal areas	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Raise river banks to avoid floods and/or leave an undeveloped area around rivers to reduce damages in the event of a flood	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Develop water resources for water supply security in case of droughts or climate-caused disruptions in the water supply.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Reinforce bridges and other structures that might get eroded or damaged by rising water levels	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Switch to drought- and climate-resistant crops	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Q.10. Whether or not they are currently being implemented, we would like you to tell us what level of priority should be given in your country, in your opinion, to each of the adaptation measures listed

below. Please rate each of them on a scale from 1 to 5, where 1=lowest or no priority and 5=highest priority.

Adaptation measure	1=lowest or no priority	2	3	4	5=highest priority	Don't know
Structures (seawalls, dams) to prevent flooding of coastal areas	1	2	3	4	5	6
Raise river banks to avoid floods and/or leave an undeveloped area around rivers to reduce damages in the event of a flood	1	2	3	4	5	6
Develop water resources for water supply security in case of droughts or climate-caused disruptions in the water supply.	1	2	3	4	5	6
Reinforce bridges and other structures that might get eroded or damaged by rising water levels	1	2	3	4	5	6
Switch to drought- and climate-resistant crops	1	2	3	4	5	6

Q11. How would you classify these adaptation measures—Infrastructure, nature-based*, institutional?

Adaptation measure	Infrastructure	Nature-based*	Institutional	I don't know
Structures (seawalls, dams) to prevent flooding of coastal areas	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Raise river banks to avoid floods and/or leave an undeveloped area around rivers to reduce damages in the event of a flood	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Develop water resources for water supply security in case of droughts or climate-caused disruptions in the water supply.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Reinforce bridges and other structures that might get eroded or damaged by rising water levels	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Switch to drought- and climate-resistant crops	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Section C. Benefits of adaptation

Q12. In your opinion, who are the likely beneficiaries of adaptation policies? Please select all that apply.

Adaptation measure	Potential beneficiaries					
	The entire nation	The local community	Specific interest groups (for example, farmers, fishermen, industry groups)	Tourists and visitors	Others, please explain	I don't know
Structures (seawalls, dams) to prevent flooding of coastal areas	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		
Raise river banks to avoid floods and/or leave an undeveloped area around rivers to reduce damages in the event of a flood	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		
Develop water resources to ensure water supply security in case of droughts or climate-caused disruptions in the water supply.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		
Reinforce bridges and other structures that might get eroded or damaged by rising water levels	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		
Switch to drought- and climate-resistant crops	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		

Section D. Cost of adaptation

Adaptation generally comes at a cost. In some cases, when people have to change their behaviours, the cost is limited to simple discomfort or annoyance. Imagine for example having to re-arrange your schedule because it is too hot to go outside during the day in the middle of a heat wave. In other cases, the cost is out-of-pocket and is incurred by individuals. This would be the case, for example, when we run the air conditioning during a heat wave, which will bring a higher electricity bill. In other cases yet, when adaptation measures are undertaken by the government, the cost is incurred by society and is spread over all taxpayers.

Q13. In what follows, we will show you a number of adaptation measures. We will ask you to identify who bears these costs in your country.

Q13.1a. The cost of building seawalls, dams and structures to protect from rising sea levels is incurred...

- by the entire nation
- by local communities.
- by firms
- by individuals
- by other groups. Please explain:
- by none of the above
- I don't know

Q13.2a. The cost of avoiding going outside when it is too hot during a heat wave is incurred...

- by the entire nation
- by local communities.
- by firms
- by individuals
- by other groups. Please explain:
- by none of the above
- I don't know

Q13.3a. The cost of suspending outdoors work (in farms, construction, etc.) when it is too hot, is incurred...

- by the entire nation
- by local communities.
- by firms
- by individuals
- by other groups. Please explain:
- by none of the above
- I don't know

Q13.4a. The cost of running the air conditioning at home when it is too hot, is incurred...

- by the entire nation
- by local communities.
- by firms
- by individuals
- by other groups. Please explain:
- by none of the above
- I don't know

Q13.5a. The cost re-arranging irrigation and changing agricultural practices is incurred...

- by the entire nation

- by local communities.
- by firms
- by individuals
- by other groups. Please explain:
- by none of the above [
- I don't know

Q13.6a. The cost of restoring wetlands to help avoid floods is incurred...

- by the entire nation
- by local communities.
- by firms
- by individuals
- by other groups. Please explain:
- by none of the above
- I don't know

Q13.8a. The cost of leaving an undeveloped area around rivers to reduce the damage in the event of a flood is incurred...

- by the entire nation
- by local communities.
- by firms
- by individuals
- by other groups. Please explain:
- by none of the above
- I don't know

Q13.9a. The cost of developing water resources to ensure water supply security in case of droughts or climate-caused disruptions in the water supply is incurred...

- by the entire nation
- by local communities.
- by firms
- by individuals
- by other groups. Please explain
- by none of the above
- I don't know

Q13.10a. The cost of reinforcing bridges and other structures that might get eroded or damaged by rising water levels is incurred...

- by the entire nation
- by local communities.
- by firms
- by individuals
- by other groups. Please explain:

by none of the above

I don't know

Q13.11a. The cost of using certain species of plants to limit runoff when it rains to protect water quality in rivers and water bodies is incurred...

by the entire nation

by local communities.

by firms

by individuals

by other groups. Please explain:

by none of the above

I don't know

Q13.12a. The cost of switching to climate-resistant crops, livestock breeds, and aquaculture breeds is incurred...

by the entire nation

by local communities.

by firms

by individuals

by other groups. Please explain:

by none of the above

I don't know

Section E. Adaptation programs

We would now like to describe a number of possible climate change adaptation programs. Scientists and engineers are currently examining a number of options, assessing their effectiveness, and estimating the costs of these programs.

These programs focus on natural resources (such as the water supply, surface waters and coastal areas) and economic activities involving natural resources, such as agriculture, fisheries and aquaculture, and forests.

We will use a stylized description, based on the points listed below:

Resources or sectors covered by the program:

- Water supply for drinking and all other residential, commercial, and industrial uses
- Surface waters (rivers, lakes, lagoons)
- Coastal areas
- Agriculture
- Fishing and aquaculture
- Forests

Type of measures adopted in the program:

Each of the above resources or sectors can rely on

- Infrastructure measures
- nature-based* measures, or
- institutional measures,

alone or in combination.

Geographical coverage:

- Percentage of the country's territory that would be covered by the program

Reduction in climate change damages delivered by the program:

- Expressed in percentage terms.

Larger percentages mean more protection from climate change damages.

Cost of the program to the taxpayer:

- additional income tax on your household, to be paid each year for a total of 10 years

We will now show you a number of programs currently under consideration that would limit the adverse consequences of climate change in your country. These programs vary in terms of coverage, types of measures, level of protection that they offer, and estimated cost.

Exact design possibilities and details and cost estimates are still being developed and evaluated by engineers and other experts at this time.

Given the scope and the cost of these programs, it is important to learn the opinions of the public about them.

We will share your opinions and those of the other participants in this study (in anonymous form) with the authorities of [COUNTRY].

Please consider the advisory referendum below. You will be asked to vote in favour or against the hypothetical adoption of a possible program. The general rules of voting apply here: If a majority of the voters were in favour, the program would be adopted and every taxpayer would pay the stated amount, which would be added to their household’s income taxes. The money collected in this way would be placed in a special account and spent only on the indicated adaptation program. (It would not be allowed to spend it on anything else.) If a majority were not reached, the program would not be adopted, and no payment would be collected from the taxpayers.

We will repeat this exercise a total of seven times. Every time you will vote a different adaptation program. Please try to evaluate each of the seven programs on their own and independently from the others. In other words, vote on each program if this was the only referendum you are voting.

We remind you that if you were prepared to spend this amount, this money would no longer be available to spend on food, clothes, transportation, vacation, etc. The costs of the program would be incurred every year for a total of 10 years. So, if a program were to cost your household 110 GBP a year for each of 10 years, at the end of the 10 years you would have paid a total of 1100 GBP.

Q14.A Would you vote in favour or against program A? If a majority of voters approved program A, it would be implemented and it would deliver the benefits listed below. You, and every other household, would have to pay the sum listed below. If a majority of the voters were against program A, the program would not be implemented, its benefits would not be experienced, and you and everyone else would pay nothing.

Program A:

Natural resource or Sector	Details
Water supply for drinking and all other residential, commercial, and industrial uses	
Surface waters (rivers, lakes, lagoons)	
Coastal areas	
Agriculture	

Forests	
Fisheries and aquaculture	
Geographical coverage:	
Percentage reduction in climate change damages	
Cost to each taxpayer	

in favour of program A

against program A

Q15.A Do you think that the benefits from the program are

Climate change adaptation,

Environmental quality

Biodiversity

Human Health

Recreation

Other, please explain

I don't know

Q14.X *Now consider program X.* Would you vote in favour or against program X? If a majority of voters approved program X, it would be implemented, and it would deliver the benefits listed below. You, and every other household, would have to pay the sum listed below. If a majority votes against program X, the program would not be implemented, its benefits would not be experienced, and you and everyone else would pay nothing. Please remember to vote on this choice independently of your previous answers.

Program X:

Natural resource or Sector	Details
Water supply for drinking and all other residential, commercial, and industrial uses	
Surface waters (rivers, lakes, lagoons)	

Coastal areas	
Agriculture	
Forests	
Fisheries and aquaculture	
Geographical coverage:	
Percentage reduction in climate change damages	
Cost to each taxpayer	

in favour of program X

against program X

Q15.X Do you think that the benefits from the program are:

Climate change adaptation,

Environmental quality

Biodiversity

Human Health

Recreation

Other, please explain

I don't know

Q.16 When choosing your preferred policy programs, was there one specific component of the programs that is **more important to you** than all others? Please select one.

The sectors in general

Water supply for drinking and all other residential, commercial, and industrial uses

Surface waters

Coastal areas

Agriculture

Fisheries and aquaculture

Forests

Geographical coverage

Percentage climate change damage reduction

Cost for the taxpayer

All components were equally important in my decision

I don't know

Q.17 When choosing your preferred policy programs, was there one specific component of the programs that was **not important at all** for your decision? Please select one.

- The sectors in general
- Water supply for drinking and all other residential, commercial, and industrial uses
- Surface waters
- Coastal areas
- Agriculture
- Fisheries and aquaculture
- Forests
- Geographical coverage
- Percentage climate change damage reduction
- Cost for the taxpayer
- All components were equally important in my decision
- I don't know

Section F. Demographics

Q.18 How many people is your household comprised of?

- 1 (just me)
- 2
- 3
- 4
- 5
- More than 5

Q18A. How many children under the age of 18 live with you at your home?

- None
- 1
- 2
- 3
- 4
- 5
- More than 5
- I prefer not to answer

Q18B. How many people aged 65 and older live with you at your home (including yourself, if your aged 65 or older)?

- None
- 1
- 2
- 3
- 4
- 5
- More than 5
- I prefer not to answer

Q19. How would you describe your current employment status?

- [1] Employed full-time
- [2] Employed part-time
- [3] Self-employed
- [4] Student
- [5] Homemaker
- [6] Employed but currently on maternity/paternity or parental leave
- [7] Retired
- [8] Unemployed, looking for work
- [9] Unable to work due to sickness or disability
- [10] Other, please specify:

[99] I prefer not to answer

Q20. Do you, or any member of your household living with you, work in one of the following sectors?

- Agriculture and/or animal husbandry
- Food processing
- Fisheries and/or aquaculture
- Forestry
- Timber industry
- Water utilities
- Maritime transport (including ports and shipyards)
- Inland water transport (including ports and shipyards)
- Local and national public administration
- Public environmental agencies and authorities
- Tourism and recreation
- none of the above
- [99] I prefer not to answer

Q.21. How likely is it, in your opinion, that the opinions you reported in this survey and those of other consumers will be taken into account by policymakers and authorities in your country? Please select your answer on a scale from 1 to 5, where 1=not likely at all and 5=very likely.

1= not likely at all	2	3	4	5= very likely	6= I don't know
1	2	3	4	5	6

ANNEX 2: DETAILS ON ONE-ON-ONE TESTS

We report here in more detail the protocol and the outcomes of the tests carried out in two waves In August 2022 and in February/March 2023.

Test participants were contacted by email to fix appointments for their remote interviews on Zoom and sent a copy of the draft questionnaire in electronic format. Interviews were recorded and notes were taken for future reference. We began each test by reminding the respondents that the interview would be recorded and asked for their explicit consent. After a short ice-breaking conversation mainly about the respondents' job (also to double check their lack of professional expertise about climate change), we briefly introduced the TransformAr project, the purpose of the survey, and why we needed to test the questionnaire. Test respondents were asked to read each explanatory text and to answer the questions. After each text box or question, we asked them if they found it clear and impartial, and if there was any part of what they just read/answered that they found problematic.

We showed them an example of a policy package described succinctly in a table format (see Table A2-1) and we asked whether this example seemed clear and reasonable and whether elements such as geographic coverage were understandable. We also asked whether people should be asked to pay an additional amount of money in the form of income tax every year (and in this case, for how many years) or rather a one-off payment, after which the resulting revenue will be used over several years.

We then asked them to compare two policy packages and to tell us which one they thought would be more effective, which one the more costly to the taxpayer. Finally, we asked them to read a short text mimicking the formal announcement of the launch of policy package and asked the test respondent to describe it using the same succinct format used in the example we proposed. This exercise was intended to evaluate the ability of the respondents to correctly identify the main components of the policy packages as described in the format we intended to use for the DCE.

We concluded the test with a series of debriefing questions, aimed at giving the test respondents an opportunity to think back to their experience with the questionnaire and elicit their feedback about clarifications and simplifications needed.

Overall, participants in this first round of one-on-one tests in Italy found the information material clear and interesting. They mostly stated to be quite at ease with questions about adaption priorities, likely benefits, adaptation costs, and familiarity with adaptation measures. They were less at ease when asked to identify who benefits from adaptation measures or who is in charge of implementing them. The DCE example was in general found clear, but when asked to play around with attributes most people found the exercise difficult. The cost attribute needed clarification – if annual, the number of years was often indicated as a crucial piece of information to be specified. They frequently related the questions with their own experiences and with the climate-related emergencies in their place of residence: people living in Venice often referred to sea level rise and the MOSE barrier that was installed to protect the lagoon; those living in southern Italy (Lecce) were often concerned about the impacts of droughts on agriculture. They often suggested the use of visual aids and/or examples to clarify questions.

Table A2-1. The policy package example shown to Italian test respondents in August 2022 (English translation)

Sector/resources	Measure
Water supply	Infrastructure measures (irrigation dikes, desalination plants, water reservoirs)
Rivers and water bodies	n.a.
Coastal areas	Infrastructure measures (barriers)
Agriculture	n.a.
Fisheries and aquaculture	n.a.
Forests	n.a.
Geographical coverage:	The whole national territory
Institution in charge	Local administration
Percentage reduction in climate change damages	50%
Cost to each taxpayer	100 euro/year

Second round of tests

Based on the results of the first round of tests and the feedback we got from project partners at TransformAr's third Consortium Meeting in Guadalupe in early December 2022, we set out to refine our questionnaire. We considered introducing visual aids for the DCE (short movies or pictures or infographics); we feared however that applying this idea to our questionnaire, would considerably increase the time needed for completion and tire the respondents. Still, we decided to inquire about the desirability of visual aids within our **second round of one-on-one tests**.

This new round involved twelve additional one-on one tests with people from the public, and were carried out in Italy, Spain, Finland, the UK and Norway between February and early March 2023.

The second round of test followed a similar protocol as the first round, but we introduced new elements to be tested. As in the first round, we began each test with some casual icebreaking conversation, followed by a brief introduction about the purpose of the survey and the testing exercise. We asked people to go through the questionnaire, answer the question and tell us if they found the exercise easy to understand and unbiased. The new elements tested in this round were the following:

- **The type of measures considered in the DCE:** We dropped research-based adaptation, to reduce the complexity of the experimental design and in consideration of the fact that such research would ultimately result in adaptation solutions pertaining to the other three categories (infrastructure, nature-based, or institutional), and we checked if test respondents were at their ease with these categories. Since during the first round of tests our respondents were quite indifferent about who is in charge, we also dropped the institution in charge of implementation (local or national authority) from the list of attributes.

- **The format of the DCE:** given the difficulty experienced by our test respondents in the first round with comparing alternatives, we resorted to a simplified DCE setting whereby just one policy package is compared to the status quo, instead of a standard DCE format where two alternatives are compared to the status quo.
- **The time dimension of costs and benefits:** we used the first half of the one-on-one tests in this round to learn about attitudes towards the payment – whether annual instalments for several years (ten years in our case) were preferable to one lump-sum payment, whereby the funds thus collected would be earmarked to finance the policy measure during the subsequent ten years. We also asked whether having to wait for a measure to be operative or knowing that some measure may come with an expiry date, would have been a problem.
- **The deployment of a mock DCE (in a referendum setting):** We asked the test respondents of the second half of the one-on-one tests in this second round, to choose among a policy package and the status quo a total of eight times, varying the sectors/resources, the type of measures and the cost, while leaving geographic coverage and damages restored always unchanged. The purpose of this exercise was both to check the feasibility of the referendum format for the DCE and the identification of a realistic range of values for the payments. To take care of strategic behaviour, the rules of the game were carefully explained, and test respondents were asked to answer each referendum question independently from the previous ones.
- **The geographical coverage of the policy package:** we investigated what people understand for the fraction of the territory covered by the policy package. We inquired whether they understood it as uniformly distributed over the national territory, or over the territory where the relevant climate vulnerabilities are most pressing, or where most people leave.
- **The role of consequentiality:** The degree of confidence in the willingness of public authorities to take into due account the opinions expressed by respondents through this survey (consequentiality) was carefully examined. Specific language about consequentiality was introduced just before the discrete choice experiment. This is particularly important to ensure the incentive compatibility of the whole DCE exercise.

Overall, our revised questionnaire was found clear and understandable. We refer the Reader to Section 3.2 for our main takeaways from these tests and their implications for the final questionnaire.

Climate change impacts are here and now. The impacts on people, prosperity and planet are already pervasive but unevenly distributed, as stated in the new EU Blueprint strategy (European Commission-EC, 2019). To reduce climate-related risks, the EC and the IPCC agree that transformational adaptation is essential. The TransformAr project aims to develop and demonstrate products and services to launch and accelerate large-scale and disruptive adaptive process for transformational adaptation in vulnerable regions and communities across Europe.

The 6 TransformAr lighthouse demonstrators face a common challenge: water-related risks and impacts of climate change. Based on existing successful initiatives, the project will develop, test and demonstrate solutions and pathways, integrated in Innovation Packages, in 6 territories.

Transformational pathways, including an integrated risk assessment approach are co-developed by means of 9 Transformational Adaptive Blocks. A set of 22 tested actionable adaptive solutions are tested and demonstrated, ranging from nature-based solutions, innovative technologies, financing, insurance and governance models, awareness and behavioral change solutions.

TransformAr

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon H2020 innovation action programme under grant agreement 101036683.

